

RESEARCH ARTICLE

REVISED **Testing a computational model of causative overgeneralizations: Child judgment and production data from English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K'iche'** [version 2; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

How do language learners avoid the production of verb argument structure overgeneralization errors (**The clown laughed the man* c.f. *The clown made the man laugh*), while retaining the ability to apply such generalizations productively when appropriate? This question has long been seen as one that is both particularly central to acquisition research and particularly challenging. Focussing on causative overgeneralization errors of this type, a previous study reported a computational model that learns, on the basis of corpus data and human-derived verb-semantic-feature ratings, to predict adults' by-verb preferences for less- versus more-transparent

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causative forms (e.g., * *The clown laughed the man* vs *The clown made the man laugh*) across English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K'iche Mayan. Here, we tested the ability of this model (and an expanded version with multiple hidden layers) to explain binary grammaticality judgment data from children aged 4;0-5;0, and elicited-production data from children aged 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6 ($N=48$ per language). In general, the model successfully simulated both children's judgment and production data, with correlations of $r=0.5-0.6$ and $r=0.75-0.85$, respectively, and also generalized to unseen verbs. Importantly, learners of all five languages showed some evidence of making the types of overgeneralization errors – in both judgments and production – previously observed in naturalistic studies of English (e.g., **I'm dancing it*). Together with previous findings, the present study demonstrates that a simple learning model can explain (a) adults' continuous judgment data, (b) children's binary judgment data and (c) children's production data (with no training of these datasets), and therefore constitutes a plausible mechanistic account of the acquisition of verbs' argument structure restrictions.

Keywords

child language acquisition, verb semantics, causative, English, Japanese, Hindi, Hebrew, K'iche', discriminative learning

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REVISED Amendments from Version 1

The detailed changes we have made in response to the reviewers' comments are summarised in the "Notes to Reviewers" section. In brief, the main change involved the addition of a further computational modelling section in which we ran over 2,000 new models (Study 3). The aim was to investigate whether, by instantiating various limitations that correspond to those facing children, it might be possible to build a model whose verb-by-verb predictions correlate better with the judgment and production data of younger children than those of older children and adults. If so, this constitutes preliminary evidence that children's retreat from overgeneralization is a consequence of the reduction of the relevant limitation. If not, this constitutes further evidence that children's retreat from overgeneralization is a consequence of changes outside of the purview of this modeling, such as increasing executive function, which allow for better rejection and inhibition of ungrammatical forms. This second possibility was more strongly supported. All figures within the article are updated or new.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Plain language summary

When learning their native language, children often produce errors in which they use verbs in "ungrammatical" sentence types (e.g., **The clown laughed the man*), whereas an adult would say *The clown made the man laugh*). Although these examples are from English, similar errors are observed in many other languages, including Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K'iche Mayan. A previous study reported a computer model which, when trained on an approximation of real language input, simulated the relative grammatical acceptability of these errors with different verbs as judged by child and adult raters. The aim of this study was to investigate whether the same model (and a new, slightly more sophisticated version) could explain (a) binary judgments from younger children (4–5 year-olds, who were simply asked "Is this sentence acceptable" rather than "How acceptable is this sentence?") and (b) the rates at which children learning these five languages actually produce such errors for different verbs (e.g., **Someone laughed/danced/sang the boy*). In general, the model performed very well on both tasks for all languages except K'iche'.

Introduction

The question of how language learners come to avoid verb argument structure overgeneralization errors such as **The clown laughed the man* – in some cases after a protracted period of producing them – has been described as a "learnability paradox" (Pinker, 1989: 415); "one of the most...difficult challenges for all students of language acquisition" (Bowerman, 1988: 73). The problem is this: On the one hand, children need to be able to use verbs in argument structure constructions in which they have not witnessed them; this type of productivity is the hallmark of human language. On the other hand, children need to be able to constrain this generalization process in order to avoid producing ungrammatical utterances such as **The clown laughed the man*. These types of errors, in which English-speaking children incorrectly mark causation using the

transitive causative for verbs that prefer the periphrastic causative (e.g., *The clown made the man laugh*) are the focus of the present study; along with equivalent errors in Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K'iche Mayan. Further naturalistically obtained examples of this error are summarized in Table 1 below (from the diary study of Ambridge & Ambridge, 2020). Similar errors have been observed in naturalistic data for Japanese (Nakaishi, 2016; see also the experimental study of Fukuda & Fukuda, 2001), though they have not, to our knowledge, been investigated for any of the other languages included here.

This problem has attracted a great deal of research attention (Alishahi & Stevenson, 2008; Ambridge *et al.*, 2008; Ambridge *et al.*, 2009; Brooks & Zizak, 2002; Brooks *et al.*, 1999; Gropen *et al.*, 1991; Li & MacWhinney, 1996; Perfors *et al.*, 2010; Stefanowitsch, 2008; Theakston, 2004; Wonnacott *et al.*, 2008); Ambridge, 2013; Ambridge & Ambridge, 2020; Ambridge & Blything, 2016; Ambridge & Brandt, 2013; Ambridge *et al.*, 2011; Ambridge *et al.*, 2012a; Ambridge *et al.*, 2012b; Ambridge *et al.*, 2013; Ambridge *et al.*, 2014; Ambridge *et al.*, 2015; Ambridge *et al.*, 2018; Barak *et al.*, 2016; Bidgood *et al.*, 2014; Boyd & Goldberg, 2011; Blything *et al.*, 2014; Goldberg, 2011; Harmon & Kapatsinski, 2017; Hsu & Chater, 2010; Irani, 2009; Perek & Goldberg, 2017; Robenalt & Goldberg, 2015; Robenalt & Goldberg, 2016; Twomey *et al.*, 2014; Twomey *et al.*, 2016), including two book-length treatments (Goldberg, 2019; Pinker, 1989). However, until a single recent study, research on the retreat from overgeneralization had been conducted exclusively on English (and mainly on dative and locative constructions).

This recent study (Ambridge *et al.*, 2020), sought to explain how speakers learn to avoid not only causative errors in English, (e.g., **The clown laughed the man*), but also equivalent errors in Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K'iche' Mayan. It also adopted a novel theoretical approach: Previous studies had attempted to explain this phenomenon in terms of three – to some extent – competing theories: preemption, conservatism *via* entrenchment (both statistical-learning theories) and verb semantics (from Ambridge *et al.*, 2020: 2–4):

- Under the preemption hypothesis (Goldberg, 1995), the use of a particular verb in a particular target structure (e.g., *laugh* in the less-transparent structure, as in **Someone laughed the boy*) is deemed increasingly ungrammatical on the basis of occurrences of this verb in a nearly synonymous competing structure (e.g., the more-transparent structure, as in *X made Y laugh*). This account predicts a negative correlation between the acceptability of a particular error (e.g., **The clown laughed the man*) and the corpus frequency of the relevant verb root in a competing structure (e.g., *X made Y laugh*); a prediction supported, for English, by the corpus and judgment studies of Goldberg (2011) and Robenalt & Goldberg (2015); Robenalt & Goldberg (2016).
- Under the [conservatism *via*] entrenchment hypothesis (Braine & Brooks, 1995), repeated occurrences of a particular verb root (e.g., *laugh*) contribute to an

Table 1. Transitive causative overgeneralization errors produced by an English-speaking child (reproduced under a CC BY 4.0 license from Ambridge, 2019; also reproduced in Ambridge & Ambridge, 2020).

Age	Error
2;3	Can you reach me? (Already being held, wants lifting up higher to touch sparkly part of a sign)
2;4	Can you jump me off? (wants help jumping down off the bed)
2;4	Did you drop the letters? (=“Did you make the letters drop?” Foam letters stuck to the bathroom wall have fallen into the bath)
2;6	(Dad: why are you running?) It’s practising me to run like that
2;6	jump me!
2;6	Don’t swim me
2;7	Run me down, jump me down (wants to run down slide)
2;7	Jump me
2;7	Drink me. drink me, Dad! (Can’t reach juice in bottom of cup and wants it tipped right back)
2;7	I’m just dancing it (shaking the bent-double flap of the elephant’s door in Dear Zoo, to make it dance)
2;7	I can dance it (book)
2;7	I’m dancing it
2;7	This is the boat - swim it!
2;7	Swim that aeroplane (submarine)
2;7	Stay your leg up there (holding dad’s leg)
2;7	Stop jumping them (Dad is tapping rabbits in Peter Rabbit game to make them jump)
2;7	drink me a bit (wants straw held up to her mouth to drink squash in bed)
2;10	The sheet’s slipping me
2;11	Jump me, Dad! x5
2;11	I jumped my legs. I hopped my legs
3;2	I stand on your feet and you walk me
3;2	(Mum: what happens to the rubbish when it goes outside?). It gets died.
3;5	(Dad, playing with Shopkins: Now what are we doing?) Chloe: Going them in. (What?) Into the bathroom
3;6	I’m try to duck her under (pushing Aurora doll under the seat belt of Barbie car)
3;6	Pens are difficult to come off the paper
3;7	Reach me up there (wants to see toys on top shelf)
3;7	It will get died [die/get killed]
3;7	That nearly feeled me like I’m nearly falling off
3;8	I’m going it faster (exercise bike at airport)
3;8	Eat it in my mouth (pez sweet that has fallen onto floor - wants Dad to pick it up and post it into her mouth)
3;8	Disappear them and disappear them (scooping up bubbles in the bath)
3;9	Your turn to dance me, Dad (i.e., swing her around by the arms)
3;10	Those guys died Maleficent (watching Sleeping Beauty)
3;10	We died (dissolved) Mummy’s special soap didn’t we, Dad?
3;11	Jump me up there (wants putting onto the toilet seat)
3;11	I wanna jump her in (Ariel doll into bath)
3;11	It will die you; it will make you killed
4;0	Mermaids have got special powers; they can die baddies
4;7	Jump me x 2

ever-strengthening probabilistic inference that it cannot be used grammatically in structures in which it has not yet appeared (e.g., *The clown laughed the man; the transitive-causative); a kind of rational Bayesian inference from absence (e.g., Hsu *et al.*, 2017). Intuitively, one way to interpret entrenchment is the inference that “given how often I’ve heard this verb root in general, if it were permitted in this structure, I would have heard it by now”. This account predicts a negative correlation between the acceptability of a particular error (e.g., *The clown laughed the man) and the overall corpus frequency of the relevant verb root, regardless of the structure in which it occurs; a prediction supported, for English, by the corpus-judgment study of Stefanowitsch (2008).

- The *verb-semantics* hypothesis (Pinker, 1989; Shibatani & Pardeshi, 2002) starts from the assumption that the distinction between verbs that allow (or prefer) *less-versus more-transparent* causation (e.g., *break, move, roll, spin* versus *laugh, cry, fall, disappear*) is not arbitrary, but reflects the semantics of those verbs. The most straightforward characterization is that actions of the latter type (e.g., *laugh*) “have internal causes that would make any external prodding indirect” (Pinker, 1989: 302), meaning that causation can be expressed only via a dedicated, transparent causative marker (*make, -(-s)ase, -aa, hiCCiC* or *-isa-j*); and even this causation is often rather indirect (e.g., Bowerman, 1988:91 points out that *John made the baby stand up* could imply simply giving an order). In contrast, verbs of the former type (e.g., *break*) are more amenable to external causation, particularly direct, physical causation (Smith, 1970). Thus, for these verbs, causation does not require a dedicated surface marker (hence “less-transparent”). Because causation is inherent in the meaning of the verb itself (e.g., *break* already means ‘cause to become broken’), this meaning comes “for free” in a basic transitive sentence.

While each of these mechanisms enjoys considerable empirical support independently (see the reference list in the previous paragraph), Ambridge *et al.* (2020) sought to unify these theories by building a computational model that yields all three effects in a single learning mechanism.

The model developed by Ambridge *et al.* (2020) – a simple two-layer connectionist network – is trained on input-output pairs consisting of a verb (e.g., *break*) and a causative type (e.g., for English, either the transitive causative or the *make* periphrastic causative respectively), in proportion to the frequency of each in a representative input corpus (e.g., for English, the frequency of [CAUSER] [BREAK] [CAUSEE] vs [CAUSER] [MAKE] [CAUSEE] BREAK). Other corpus utterances containing the relevant verb (e.g., intransitive [ACTOR] [BREAK]) are mapped to a catch-all “Other” output node. Crucially, the input to the model consists not only of an orthogonal (one-hot) “lexical” verb representation that uniquely identifies each verb stem, but also four “semantics” units. The (continuous) activation

level of these units is set on the basis of human ratings of four semantic properties thought to be relevant to languages’ preferences for less-transparent (e.g., *X broke Y*) versus more-transparent (*X made Y break*) causative forms respectively (e.g., Shibatani & Pardeshi, 2002)¹. These semantic ratings were obtained by showing native adult speakers of each language an animation depicting the action described by each verb (though they were not given the verb itself) and asking them to rate:

Event-merge: The extent to which the causing and caused event are two separate events or merge into a single event that happens at a single time and a single point in space

Autonomy of the causee

Requires: Whether the caused event requires a causer

Directive: Whether causation is directive (e.g., giving an order) or physical

It is important to note that the model was not given any information regarding human judgments of the grammatical acceptability of the more- and less-transparent causative forms of each verb (which would make its learning task trivially simple, and akin to a conventional statistically regression model conducted on participants’ grammaticality judgments). Rather, the model was trained to “predict” the forms that occurred in a suitable corpus for each language. For example, if the English corpus contained the utterance *You broke it*, the target output was [1,0,0] for the less-transparent, more-transparent and “other” output nodes respectively; the corresponding input node values were [0,0,1,0,0,0,...] on the lexical nodes (indicating “break”), [1] on the causative node (indicating causative), and [0.90, 0.90, 0.87, 0.85] for the semantic units corresponding to event-merge, autonomy, requires and directive.

Having learned the input-output mappings for the corpus, the model was – at test – presented with each verb ($N=60$) and interrogated for its prediction of a causative form (e.g., for English, transitive causative vs periphrastic causative with *make*; **Someone laughed the boy* vs *Someone made the boy laugh*). The resulting activation level of the corresponding output units was taken as the model’s “grammaticality judgment” for that form. These judgments were then correlated against those obtained from native speakers of each language ($N=48$ at each of ages 5–6, 9–10 and adults). Note, again, that the model never saw these judgments, having been trained only a suitable input corpus for that language.

Because we adopt the same model in the present article, it is important to fully set out here the details of its architecture. In fact, although Ambridge *et al.* (2020) described

¹The periphrastic causative form is termed the more-transparent form because it includes an overt causative marker (*make*). More- and less-transparent causative forms for Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K’iche’ are set out in the Methods section.

their model as a discriminative-learning model that used the Widrow-Hoff learning rule (p.17), this was an error. While the model resembled discriminative learning models in its absence of any hidden layers, it actually used the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) learning rule. Because the model's task was to choose, on each learning trial, between a set of mutually exclusive output nodes, the softmax activation function was used. The model did not have a learning-rate parameter; the only free parameters were range, which specifies the range of the initial random weights, and weight decay, both set to 0.5 for all simulations. These settings were not varied systematically, although informal experimentation revealed (a) that (near-) zero settings for decay harmed the model's performance (presumably by causing the model to over-fit the training data) but (b) changes to the initial random weights made no difference (presumably because the results are always averaged across 48 runs with different initial weights).

In general, the model reported in Ambridge *et al.* (2020) achieved correlations of around $r=0.75$ with human judgments, showing only a small decrement in performance (i.e., slightly lower correlations) when tested on verbs that had been withheld during training, using split-half validation. (Though note that this "split half validation" did NOT consist of training the model on half of the participants' grammaticality judgments and having it predict the held-out half. Rather, it consisted of withholding half of the verbs from the corpus-derived training set, before interrogating it for its predictions for the held-out verbs). This finding demonstrates that the model, like human learners, eventually reaches a point at which it is able to produce the appropriate causative form for verbs that it is encountering for the first time, on the basis of their semantics. Importantly, prior to this point, the model displays an "overgeneralization" stage analogous to that shown by children (at least for English). For example, when presented with *laugh*, the English model initially produces the transitive causative construction (e.g., **Someone laughed the boy*) with considerably higher probability than the periphrastic causative (e.g., *Someone made the boy laugh*). After around 12 epochs of training (each consisting of 10,000 corpus utterances) the probabilities begin to flip, and the model asymptotes at predictions of around 0.7 vs 0.3 for the periphrastic- versus transitive-causative respectively ("Other" uses are around zero, since the model is interrogated for a causative form).

While these findings constitute support for the model developed by Ambridge *et al.* (2020), this support is currently limited in three ways.

First, the model was assessed only on its ability to predict grammaticality judgment data obtained from older children (5–6 and 9–10 years) and adults. However, the available English data (e.g., Ambridge & Ambridge, 2020; Bowerman, 1988; Pinker, 1989) suggest that the majority of such overgeneralization errors are produced before this age. Indeed, for languages other than English, there is no more than anecdotal evidence that children produce such errors at all (either at age 5–6 or younger). Thus, while the model does well at explaining which forms are ungrammatical for adults and older children, it remains to be seen whether it really explains the *retreat* from

overgeneralization, which is well underway – and perhaps largely completed – by age 5.

Second, and relatedly, although the model of Ambridge *et al.* (2020) simulated the retreat from overgeneralization in a macro sense (e.g., initially predicting **Someone laughed the boy over Someone made the boy laugh*), at no stage does it predict children's verb-by-verb acceptability judgments better than adults'. Again, this calls into question the extent to which it is truly simulating the *retreat* from overgeneralization.

Third, and again relatedly, Ambridge *et al.* (2020) used only a single model architecture with a single set of parameter values. Thus, it remains to be seen whether other architectures and settings – including those designed to more closely reflect children's memory and processing limitations – might better simulate the child data; and perhaps even the developmental changes observed between childhood and adulthood.

The present study therefore has three aims. The first is to test the ability of the computational model developed by Ambridge *et al.* (2020) to explain (Study 1) grammaticality judgment data from younger children than those tested previously; children aged 4;0-5;0, which necessitates the use of a binary judgment task (rather than the Likert-scale task used with children aged 5;6-6;6) and (Study 2) children's production data, including possible overgeneralization errors, at ages 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6. The second aim (Studies 1–2) is to investigate, with these data from younger children in hand, whether the model of Ambridge *et al.* (2020) can explain development, i.e., the retreat from overgeneralization from childhood to adulthood. The third aim (Study 3) is to investigate whether other model architectures, including more advanced multiple-layer models, explain both these cross-sectional and developmental patterns of judgment and production data.

Ethics statement

For both Study 1 and Study 2, ethics approval was obtained from the University of Liverpool (approval number RETH001041), as the institution with overall responsibility for the project, and from local ethics committees at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem (22032020), the International Institute of Information Technology Hyderabad (IIITH/IEC/2016/1), and the Universidad del Valle de Guatemala (¿Cómo los niños adquieren la estructura de oraciones en K'iche'?). Japanese universities do not routinely provide ethics review for psychological or linguistic research. In lieu, we therefore obtained a review from Shunzo Majima, Associate Professor at the Center for Applied Ethics and Philosophy, Hokkaido University. Parents/caregivers gave informed written consent on behalf of their children, who provided verbal assent. Written consent included both participation in the study and inclusion of the data in an anonymized publicly-available dataset.

Study 1: Binary grammaticality judgments (4;0-5;0) Methods

Preregistration. The sample size, materials, data collection methods and analysis plan were pre-registered at <https://osf.io/qhnjk>, on 15th May 2018, before data collection began. We deviate here from our planned data analysis plan, which was designed

to constitute separate tests of the preemption, entrenchment and verb semantics hypothesis. In our view, such an analysis is no longer meaningful, given that (a) Ambridge *et al.* (2020) reported extremely high levels of collinearity between the preemption and entrenchment predictors ($r=0.75-0.96$ for difference scores, depending on the language) and (b) our goal is now to test the computational model of Ambridge *et al.* (2020) which collapses the distinction between preemption, entrenchment and verb semantics into a single learning mechanism. That said, the analyses we report are “pre-registered” in the sense that they correspond directly to those reported in the computational modeling section of Ambridge *et al.* (2020); the only difference being that the by-verb predictor variable averages across participants’ binary grammaticality judgments (Study 1) or binary production data (Study 2), rather than continuous grammaticality judgments. As such, other than the decision to switch to these analyses in the first place, we have retained no researcher degrees of freedom (Wicherts *et al.*, 2016). To be explicit, we are not switching our analysis plan because the original plan failed to yield a particular pattern of results: We have not conducted the analyses specified in the original analysis plan.

Computational model. The model architecture was identical to that reported in Ambridge *et al.* (2020; see the present Introduction for a brief outline), though new model runs were conducted (48 runs for each of 50 epochs, for each language, as in Ambridge *et al.*, 2020).

Participants. Our preregistered analysis plan said that we would recruit 48 children aged 4;0-5;0 for each language: English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K’iche’. We achieved this target for every language except K’iche’ ($N=32$), for which testing had to be terminated early due to the coronavirus pandemic. All children were native learners of the relevant language, although many would have had some limited exposure to English (particularly the Hindi-speakers) and – for K’iche’ speakers – Spanish. The target sample of $N=48$ per language was specified in the initial grant application, but was arrived at informally on the basis of the first author’s previous work, not a power calculation. Children were recruited via schools/nurseries in the UK, Israel, India, Japan and Guatemala. Parents/caregivers were sent an invitation letter and consent form. Parents/caregivers were asked not to volunteer if their children had any known or suspected language difficulties, or were not native learners of the relevant language.

Stimuli and materials. The sentences used in the grammaticality judgment task, along with the animations used to illustrate their intended meanings, were identical to those used in Ambridge *et al.* (2020), to which the reader is referred for a detailed description. The full set of sentences for each language can be viewed at <https://osf.io/84qjh/>, and the accompanying animations at <https://osf.io/x6hyw/>. Each sentence included either the more- or less-transparent causative form of one of the standardized set of 60 verbs (i.e., translational equivalents across languages) used in Ambridge *et al.* (2020), always with “Someone” as the causal subject (e.g., *Someone made the boy laugh*; **Someone laughed the boy*). Further examples, for the verb laugh, are shown for each language in Table 2. The accompanying animations depicted the caused event, but not the causer, who was obscured using stage curtains. For example, for the sentences shown in Table 2, the animation depicted a boy alone on a stage; the curtains then closed and reopened to show the boy laughing.

Procedure. Data were collected between January 2018 and March 2020 in schools and nurseries in the UK, Israel, India, Japan and Guatemala. Because the full set of 120 judgments would have been too onerous for young children, each child completed 60 judgments – more- and less-transparent forms for each of 30 verbs – according to one of four counterbalance lists (which can be viewed at <https://osf.io/hsm3b/>). These 60 judgments were split into two sessions of 30, given either on different days or on the same day with a break in between. For each child, 16 (or 14) verbs were rated in both more- and less-transparent form in the same session; the remaining 14 (or 16) verbs were rated in more-transparent form in one session and less-transparent form in the other session. A video of the procedure can be found at <https://osf.io/fqyps/>.

The procedure, which involved the child placing a small animal toy on a green tick or a red cross, indicating “grammatical” and “ungrammatical”, respectively (Theakston, 2004), is best summarized by the instructions that were given to children (in translation):

- We are going to play a game. This dog is trying to learn to speak English (/Hindi etc.). So, we’re going to watch some short videos, and he’s going to tell us what’s happening. We have to help him by telling him when he says it right, and when he gets it wrong and says it a bit funny. In the game, we will watch a cartoon

Table 2. Less-transparent and more-transparent causative sentences for the verb LAUGH for each language. For the more-transparent causative, the overt causative marker is shown in bold type.

	Less-transparent causative	More-transparent causative
English	*Someone laughed the boy	Someone made the boy laugh
Hebrew	*Mishehu caxak et ha-yeled	Mishehu hicx ik et ha-yeled
Hindi	*kisii=ne laRke=ko hããs-aa	kisii=ne laRke=ko hãs- aa -yaa
Japanese	Dareka ga otokonoko o warawasu	Dareka ga otokonoko o waraw aseru
K’iche’	x-0-u-tze’-j le ak’al le achi	x-0-u-tze’n- isa -j le ak’al le achi

and the dog will tell us what happens. We have to listen to the dog and then if he says something that sounds okay we put the toy on the tick **[demonstrates to child]** and if he says something that sounds a bit silly then we put the toy on the cross **[demonstrates to child, then completes practice trials 1 (tick) and 2 (cross). Child completes practice trials 3 (tick) and 4 (cross)]**. We're going to play the game again, but this time the cartoons are going to look a bit different **[shows still of animation]**. They're going to have either this little boy or something else on this stage. These big red curtains are going to close, and you have to imagine that there is someone is behind the curtains and that person is going to do something to make something change, so that when the curtains reopen you can see how its changed. So, let's see how this one changes. **[plays example animation: dress]**. So as you can see, in this cartoon the person behind the curtains has done something to help or make the boy get dressed. So, when we play the game again all the sentences our dog is going to say are going to start with someone and that is who the someone is, the person behind the curtains. But we're going to play the game the same where we watch the cartoon, the dog says the sentence and we listen and then we put the toy on the tick if it sounds okay or the cross if it sounds a bit silly. You've also got this grid. To win the game you need to fill all these boxes with a sticker. You'll get a sticker every time you hear this sound **[plays dog barking sound effect]**. Once there is a sticker in all of the boxes you win.

The practice trials referred to are (1) *The cat drank the milk*, (2) **The dog the ball played with*, (3) *The frog caught the fly*, (4) **His teeth the man brushed* (or sentences with equivalent word order errors in the other languages). The example animation with *dress* was created solely for use as an example, and did not appear in the main stimulus set (or in Study 2). The barking sound effect was automatically triggered by the software displaying the animations (PsychoPy 2; Peirce *et al.*, 2019), such that the child completed her grid and won the game on the final trial of each day. The experimenter also used this software to record the child's response for each trial (grammatical, ungrammatical, equivocal/refused to answer). Responses of the latter type, which were very rare, were discarded for all statistical analyses.

Analysis. All analyses were conducted in *R* (version 3.6.3; R Core Team, 2020). All computational models were built using the *nnet* package (version 7.3-14; Venables & Ripley, 2002). Correlations were conducted using the *cor* function of base *R*. All plots were made using *ggplot2* (version 2.2.1; Wickham, 2016).

Results: Binary grammaticality judgments (4;0-5;0)

Before proceeding to test the computational model, it is instructive to compare children's binary judgment data against the gold-standard adult continuous judgment data reported by

Ambridge *et al.* (2020) in order to determine (a) whether children aged 4;0-5;0 give meaningful judgments and (b) whether they make judgments that correspond to overgeneralization errors, rating as "acceptable" sentences that receive low acceptability ratings from adults.

These data are plotted in Figure 1–Figure 2 for less-transparent forms (e.g., **Someone laughed the boy*) and more-transparent forms (e.g., *Someone made the boy laugh*) respectively. The x-axis shows, for each verb form, the mean acceptability rating given by adults on the five-point scale. The y-axis shows, for each verb form, the proportion of children accepting that form (recall that each child makes only a single binary acceptability judgment for each form). Forms are colour coded to indicate child judgments that correspond to "overgeneralization errors" at the group level. This was done by converting by-verb mean adult acceptability judgments and by-verb child acceptability proportions into Z-scores, and subtracting the former from the latter. A large positive score (red) represents overgeneralization. For example, in Figure 1 (less-transparent forms), English *dance* and *sing* are red, since around 75% of children deemed **Someone danced the boy* and **Someone sang the boy* to be acceptable, despite the fact that adults assigned mean acceptability ratings close to the minimum possible (1/5) for both. A large negative score (blue) represents "undergeneralization" (i.e., children considering a form to be *less* acceptable than it is for adults). For example, in Figure 1 (less-transparent forms), English *break* and *crush* are blue, since only around 30–40% of children deemed *Someone broke the truck* and *Someone crushed the can to be acceptable* (close to 5/5 for adults).

Figure 3 shows the corresponding data for difference scores (calculated as less- minus more-transparent). This figure is colour coded such that, for green verbs, children's (binary) difference scores effectively match adults' (continuous) judgment scores, while red verbs constitute child "overgeneralization" errors in either direction. For example, English *dance* is shown in red because children show very close to zero preference for *Someone made the boy dance* over **Someone danced the boy*, while adults show a preference of around 3 points on the 5-point scale. Conversely, English *steal* is also shown in red because children show very close to zero preference for *Someone stole the jewellery* over **Someone made the jewellery steal*, while adults show a difference of around 4 points on the 5-point scale. English *freeze* on the other hand is shown in green because children – just like adults – show essentially no preference for *Someone froze the water* over *Someone made the water freeze*; i.e., both children and adults deem both forms to be more-or-less equally acceptable.

Comparison of Figure 1–Figure 2 against Figure 3 suggests an intriguing and important pattern. At first glance – i.e., looking only at their raw judgments (Figure 1–Figure 2) – children, for all five languages, seem to make a considerable number of "overgeneralization errors"; i.e., accepting forms that adults deem ungrammatical. When we look at difference scores (Figure 3), however, quite a different pattern emerges: for all five languages, the vast majority of verbs are coloured green, showing

Figure 1. Child binary judgments (present study) versus adult continuous judgments for less-transparent forms.

that children’s judgments generally mirror those of adults. What is giving rise to this apparently paradoxical pattern? In fact, there is no paradox: the overall pattern can be explained by assuming that, as a group, (a) children’s underlying grammatical knowledge is essentially adultlike by this age, but (b) children are more tolerant than adults of forms that deviate from that underlying grammar. As an example, consider the English verb *laugh*. As a group, English-speaking 4–5-year olds know that **Someone laughed the boy* is considerably less acceptable than *Someone made the boy laugh* (with a difference score of around -0.4; see Figure 3). Nevertheless, in absolute terms, English-speaking 4–5-year olds are relatively tolerant of **Someone laughed the boy* with around 60% judging it as acceptable (see Figure 1; the difference score of -0.4 arises because close to 100% of children accept *Someone made the boy laugh*; Figure 2).

In order to verify this pattern statistically, we ran a series of mixed-effects models using the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015) with the following (example) syntax:

```
English_Less=glmer(Rating ~ Adult_Less_Transparent + Valence
+(1||verb) + (1+Adult_Less_Transparent+Valence||participant),
data=subset(English, type=="Less_Transparent"), family="binomial"
(link="logit"), control=glmerControl(optimizer="bobyqa",opt
Ctrl=list(maxfun=2e5)))
```

In order to ensure a consistent model structure across languages and analyses (raw/difference scores), we did not construct the maximal converging model in each case, but instead adopted a near-maximal structure with random intercepts for verb and participant, and by-participant random slopes for adult-ratings and verb valence ratings. Verb valence ratings (from Warriner et al., 2013) were included as a control predictor, since the researchers who worked with the children expressed concern that children’s ratings seemed to be affected by the social desirability of the actions (particularly for crosslinguistically less-transparent-prefering verbs like *break*, *steal*, *crush*, *burn* etc.). All predictors were scaled and centered such that the intercept represents the adult acceptability rating for a (hypothetical) verb with the mean raw acceptability rating/difference

Figure 2. Child binary judgments (present study) versus adult continuous judgments for more-transparent forms.

score, and mean valence (i.e., neither particularly desirable or undesirable in terms of the action described). For the raw binary-acceptability models (corresponding to Figure 1–Figure 2), binomial models were used, as per the syntax above (which automatically generates p values via the z distribution). For difference-score models, where the possible responses for a given verb pair (less-/more-transparent form) are 1, 0 and -1, linear models were used, and p values calculated via the t distribution (lmerTest package; Kuznetsova *et al.*, 2017).

The models are summarized in Table 3–Table 5. Focussing on difference scores (Table 5), the adult continuous judgments are highly significantly predictive of children’s binary judgments (at $p=0.001$ or better) for English, Hebrew and Hindi; but not for Japanese and K’iche’, where children are heavily influenced by valence (also significant for Hindi): the less acceptable the action, the more children prefer the more transparent form; (e.g., *making something break*, which hints at unintentionality, is more acceptable than *breaking something*, which suggests a more intentional act). Similarly for raw ratings (Table 3–Table 4), for English, Hebrew and Hindi the adult continuous judgments are significantly predictive of children’s binary

judgments (at $p=0.001$ or better) for less-transparent, more-transparent or both forms. Notice however that, for raw ratings, the intercept is always positive – for four out of 10 models significantly so – indicating that, as suggested by Figure 1–Figure 2, children are more lenient in their acceptability judgments than are adults.

To sum up, then, at least for English, Hebrew and Hindi (for Japanese and K’iche’, children were overly affected by valence) 4–5-year-old children seem to have generally adult-like grammatical knowledge (i.e., children’s acceptability judgments are very well predicted by adults’) but also – sitting atop that knowledge – a tendency to over-accept forms that adults reject. Why?

One possibility is that children’s over-acceptance of ungrammatical forms (relative to adults) results from the use of a meta-linguistic task. For example, in a categorization task Kapatsinski, Olejarczuk and Redford (2017) found that 9–10-year-old children are more accepting than are adults of new exemplars that deviate from previous exemplars of the categories. Focussing specifically on the present task, children might

Figure 3. Child binary judgments (present study) versus adult continuous judgments for difference scores (less- minus more-transparent).

be reluctant to “correct” or “hurt the feelings of” the talking dog who produced the forms. A second possibility is that, at least beyond age 4–5, children’s underlying grammatical knowledge (at least in this particular domain) is essentially adultlike, and the solution to the no-negative-evidence problem lies not with grammatical learning, but with increasing meta-linguistic and/or meta-cognitive abilities. These might take the form of, for example, an increasing willingness to judge others’ utterances as unacceptable, or improvements in executive function that allow children to inhibit their own tendency to overgeneralization (whether in judgments or production). Anecdotally at least, children do sometimes correct their errors spontaneously, particularly when adults repeat children’s errors back to them. The production and computational modeling studies reported later in this paper are key to teasing apart these possibilities.

Moving on to the tests of the computational model, Figure 4–Figure 8 plot – for English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K’iche’, respectively – model-child correlations for (a) the full set of 60 verbs, and (b) the split-half validation test (30 verbs, randomly selected for each run). Again, it is important to stress that the split-half validation test did NOT consist of training the model on half of the participants’ grammaticality judgments and having it predict the held-out half. Rather, it consisted of withholding half of the verbs from the

corpus-derived training set, before interrogating it for its predictions for the held-out verbs. The figures also plot the developmental pattern shown by the model for a number of example verbs. For children’s judgments, the dependent measure is again the proportion of children judging the particular verb form (more-/less-transparent) to be acceptable on the binary judgment task (or a less-minus-more-transparent difference score). The predictor variable is the mean activation level of the corresponding unit of the model (or a difference score calculated in the same way).

In general, the model does a good job of predicting children’s binary judgment data, though less so than for adults’ continuous judgment data (Ambridge *et al.*, 2020, reported correlations mainly in the region of $r=0.75$). For the present binary judgment data, focussing on difference scores, the model achieved correlations in the region of $r=0.5$ – $r=0.6$ for the English, Hebrew and Hindi child data, both for seen verbs and in the split-half validation test. All six correlations are comfortably statistically significant at $p<0.01$ (Critical r [df = 58] value for $p<0.05=0.21$; for $p<0.01=0.30$ [one tailed]). The model fares less well at predicting the raw proportions of “acceptable” judgments for less- and more-transparent causative forms; though with r values in the region of $r=0.25$ – $r=0.5$, all twelve correlations are again statistically significant.

Table 3. Binary judgment task. Mixed effects models for less-transparent forms.

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
English				
(Intercept)	0.31	0.12	2.66	0.008
Adult_Less_Transparent	0.35	0.11	3.19	0.001
Valence	0.38	0.10	3.68	0.000
Hebrew				
(Intercept)	0.03	0.19	0.15	0.883
Adult_Less_Transparent	0.46	0.16	2.91	0.004
Valence	0.09	0.10	0.88	0.379
Hindi				
(Intercept)	0.10	0.12	0.81	0.417
Adult_Less_Transparent	0.42	0.08	5.02	0.000
Valence	0.16	0.08	1.89	0.059
Japanese				
(Intercept)	0.16	0.15	1.07	0.284
Adult_Less_Transparent	-0.05	0.06	-0.81	0.421
Valence	0.21	0.06	3.24	0.001
K'iche'				
(Intercept)	0.90	0.20	4.55	0.000
Adult_Less_Transparent	0.00	0.10	-0.01	0.992
Valence	0.26	0.08	3.18	0.001

Table 4. Binary judgment task. Mixed effects models for more-transparent forms.

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
English				
(Intercept)	0.06	0.11	0.56	0.572
Adult_More_Transparent	0.09	0.10	0.97	0.334
Valence	0.43	0.08	5.06	0.000
Hebrew				
(Intercept)	-0.02	0.19	-0.08	0.934
Adult_More_Transparent	0.40	0.09	4.46	0.000
Valence	0.15	0.08	1.80	0.072
Hindi				
(Intercept)	0.70	0.14	4.86	0.000
Adult_More_Transparent	0.45	0.11	3.94	0.000

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
Valence	0.36	0.11	3.28	0.001
Japanese				
(Intercept)	0.13	0.16	0.82	0.414
Adult_More_Transparent	-0.06	0.08	-0.75	0.455
Valence	0.25	0.09	2.61	0.009
K'iche'				
(Intercept)	0.96	0.25	3.86	0.000
Adult_More_Transparent	0.09	0.09	0.93	0.354
Valence	0.27	0.13	2.02	0.043

Table 5. Binary judgment task. Mixed effects models for difference scores (less minus more transparent).

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
(Intercept)	0.06	0.02	45.47	2.95	0.005
Adult_Difference_Score	0.09	0.03	52.52	3.49	0.001
Valence	-0.01	0.02	33.17	-0.57	0.572
(Intercept)	0.51	0.04	52.58	14.24	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	0.06	0.02	33.20	3.79	0.001
Valence	-0.01	0.02	43.56	-0.74	0.464
(Intercept)	0.37	0.03	67.74	13.25	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	0.08	0.02	48.78	3.90	0.000
Valence	-0.06	0.02	57.58	-3.08	0.003
(Intercept)	0.48	0.03	58.16	15.66	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	0.00	0.02	38.37	-0.08	0.934
Valence	-0.06	0.02	47.40	-2.92	0.005
(Intercept)	0.33	0.04	32.44	8.39	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	0.00	0.02	28.67	-0.09	0.931
Valence	-0.05	0.02	24.54	-2.24	0.035

For Japanese and K'iche' the model achieves only one significant correlation, for more-transparent causative forms in Japanese. The poor performance of the K'iche' model was to be expected on the basis of [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) who found similar results for adults, which they attributed to difficulties with obtaining reliable corpus counts and semantic ratings. Additionally the poor performance of both the Japanese and K'iche' models probably reflects the fact that – as noted above – both the Japanese- and K'iche' speaking children seemed to be overly affected by valence when giving acceptability judgments.

Computational model for English

Figure 4. Model-child correlations for English binary judgment data.

Computational model for Hebrew

Figure 5. Model-child correlations for Hebrew binary judgment data.

Figure 6. Model-child correlations for Hindi binary judgment data.

Computational model for Japanese

Figure 7. Model-child correlations for Japanese binary judgment data.

Figure 8. Model-child correlations for K'iche' binary judgment data.

Despite the apparent success of the computational model (at least for English, Hebrew and Hindi), it is important to note that it does not in fact explain development, or the retreat from overgeneralization, at least at the verb-by-verb level. At the macro level, the model does incorrectly predict the less- over more-transparent causative form for some verbs that prefer the latter (e.g., English *come*, *cry* and *laugh*) before correctly flipping its preference (see the bottom panels of [Figure 4–Figure 8](#)). However, at no stage does the model predict children’s judgments better than it does adults’ judgments. Indeed, if anything, it is a better model of the adult end state than it is of a child in the throes of overgeneralization (recall that [Ambridge et al., 2020](#), reported model-human correlations mainly in the region of $r=0.75$ for adults as compared to only around $r=0.5$ here). Then again, given the close correlation between adult and child judgments reported above, it may be that, at least by age 4–5, there is very little true overgeneralization – as opposed to across-the-board acceptance in a judgment task – for the model to explain.

Discussion: Binary grammaticality judgments (4;0-5;0)

Data from the binary judgment task show that, with the apparent exception of Japanese, children aged 4;0-5;0 are capable of providing meaningful grammatical acceptability judgments for sentences containing more- and less-transparent causative verb forms, though they also show some evidence of judgments that correspond to overgeneralization errors. The computational model developed by [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) successfully explained children’s judgment data for English, Hebrew and Hindi. Its failure to do so for K’iche’ and Japanese appears to be largely attributable to valence effects in children’s judgment data. However, these findings leave unanswered three questions: (1) Do children learning each of these languages actually produce these types of overgeneralization errors and, if so, (2) Can the computational model developed by [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) explain their by-verb patterning and – crucially – (3) their development (i.e., the retreat from overgeneralization)?

Study 2: Elicited production (4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6)

Methods

Preregistration. As for Study 1, the sample size, materials, data collection methods and analysis plan were pre-registered at <https://osf.io/qhnjk> before data collection began. Again, we depart here from our data-analysis plan in order to test the computational model of [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) which we judge to supersede the single-learning theories tested in our original pre-registration.

Computational model. As for Study 1, the model architecture was identical to that reported in [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) though new model runs were conducted (again, 48 runs for each of 50 epochs, for each language).

Participants. As per our preregistration, we recruited 48 children at each of ages 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6 for each language (including K’iche’). Children were recruited from the same populations as Study 1, though none took part in both studies. Sample size criteria, eligibility criteria, and sources and methods of participant selection were the same as for Study 1.

Stimuli and materials. This study used a priming methodology, in order to encourage children to attempt to produce both less- and more-transparent causative forms for each of 60 target verbs (the same set used in Study 1 and [Ambridge et al., 2020](#)). For each language, a further 60 verbs – 30 each that prefer the more- and less-transparent causative form – were selected for use as prime verbs, and corresponding animations created (following the same format as the animations for the target verbs). Only 60 prime verb were necessary, because – as for Study 1 – each child completed only half of the total number of target trials: That is, for each of 30 verbs – according to eight counterbalance lists – children described a causal animation following priming with (a) a more-transparent causative and (b) a less-transparent causative. As for Study 1, children completed two separate sessions. For each child, 16 (or 14) of the verbs appeared following both more- and less-transparent causative primes in the same session; the remaining 16 (or 14) appeared following a more-transparent causative prime in one session and a less-transparent causative prime in the other.

Procedure. Data were collected between January 2018 and March 2020 in schools and nurseries in the UK, Israel, India, Japan and Guatemala. A video of the production priming procedure can be found at <https://osf.io/hqr9p/>. Again, the procedure, is best summarized by the instructions that were given to children (in translation):

We are going to play a game. We’re going to watch some short videos and take it in turns telling this dog what has happened. The dog has either my card or your card: If we hear this sound [**plays howl sound effect**] then he has mine, if we hear this [**plays bark sound effect**] then he has yours. Then we can put our card on the grid and whoever fills their grid first wins the whole game. Our videos are going to look a bit like this. There is a stage like one you would see in a theatre with big red curtains [**plays an example animation: dress**]. So, as you can see, there was a little boy on the stage and he has no top on [**shows still of the stage at the beginning**] and when the curtains reopened he had a top on [**shows still of the stage at the end**]. You must imagine that when the curtains are closed that there is someone behind the curtains [**shows the closed curtains**]. So, in this one there was someone behind the curtains that did something to get the boy dressed. Let’s start with some practice ones and I’ll help you:

Practice trial 1 – (*dress and wrap*)

Experimenter: “someone dressed the boy”

Experimenter: “someone wrapped the present” [**encourages child to repeat**]

Practice trial 2 – (*hiccup and jump*)

Experimenter: “someone made the boy hiccup”

Experimenter: “someone made the boy jump” [**encourages child to repeat**]

Practice trial 3 – (*free and close*)

Experimenter: “someone freed the boy” [waits for/encourages child to produce...]

Child: “Someone closed the door” [experimenter corrects if necessary]

Practice trial 4 – (burp and drink)

Experimenter: “someone made the boy burp” [waits for/encourages child to produce...]

Child: “someone made the boy drink” [experimenter corrects if necessary]

The child and experimenter then completed the test trials in the same way. Note that the training trials were designed to give the child practice at producing less- and more-transparent causative forms following less- and more-transparent causative primes respectively. As for Study 1, the training verbs/animations did not feature in the test trials, and the barking/howling sound effects were automatically triggered by the software displaying the animations (Processing 2; <https://processing.org/>), such that the child completed her grid and won the game on the final trial of each day. Children’s responses were coded as to whether they included a more-transparent or less-transparent

form of the target verb, with all other responses (e.g., intransitive use of the target verb; use of a different verb; no response) treated as missing data.

Analysis. All analyses were conducted in R (version 3.6.3; R Core Team, 2020). All computational models were built using the *nnet* package (version 7.3-14; Venables & Ripley, 2002). Correlations were conducted using the *cor* function of base R. All plots were made using *ggplot2* (version 2.2.1; Wickham, 2016).

Results: Elicited production (4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6)

As for Study 1, before proceeding to test the computational model, it is instructive to compare children’s data against the gold-standard adult continuous judgment data reported by Ambridge *et al.* (2020) in order to determine (a) whether children’s productions generally seem to follow the constraints of the adult grammar and (b) whether they nevertheless produce overgeneralization errors that correspond to those observed (for English) in naturalistic data.

These data are plotted in Figure 9 (children aged 4;0-5;0) and Figure 10 (children aged 5;6-6;6). The x-axis shows, for each verb form, adults’ mean difference score (preference for less-over more-transparent causative forms). The y-axis shows the

Figure 9. Children’s (4;0-5;0) elicited productions (present study) versus adult continuous judgments.

Figure 10. Children’s (5;6-6;6) elicited productions (present study) versus adult continuous judgments.

proportion of trials on which children, as a group, produced the less- versus more-transparent causative form of each verb (recall that all other responses were discarded as missing data).

Overgeneralization errors, this time in production, are colour coded in the same way as for Study 1 (i.e., green=adultlike, red=overgeneralization in either direction). As for the binary judgment data difference-scores analysis, overgeneralization errors are – on the whole – notable mainly by their absence, particularly for the older children. Such errors do occur. For example, around 20% of English 4–5-year olds’ causative forms with *sing* used the less transparent form (e.g., **Someone sang the boy*), which is highly dispreferred for adults (c.f., *Someone made the boy sing*). Conversely around 20% of English 4–5-year olds’ causative forms with *throw* used the more transparent form (e.g., **Someone made the ball throw*), which is highly dispreferred for adults (c.f. *Someone threw the ball*). Nevertheless, even for these more error-prone verbs, performance was largely adultlike, with around 80% of 4–5-year-olds’ responses using the preferred adult form. The picture was similar across languages with only a handful of verbs (e.g., *dissolve* for Japanese, *crawl* and *whisper* for Hindi, *speak* and *boil* for Japanese, *come*, *play* and *sing* for K’iche’) dramatically deviating

from the adult reference point, when aggregating across 4–5-year-old children. By age 5–6, the picture looks even more adultlike, with Hebrew *dissolve* the only real exception.

These findings suggest that, as we tentatively concluded on the basis of the binary judgment data, children’s underlying grammatical knowledge in this domain is essentially adultlike by age 4-5, although at least some children have a higher tolerance than do adults – in production as well as judgments – for forms that deviate from this underlying grammar.

In order to verify this pattern statistically, we again ran a series of mixed-effects models in lme4, this time with the following (example) syntax:

```
(DV ~ Adult_Less_Transparent*AgeGroup +prime_type+ Valence +(0+AgeGroup|verb) + (1+Adult_Less_Transparent||participant)+ (1+prime_type||participant) , data=English, family="binomial"(link="logit"), control=glmerControl(optimizer = "bobyqa", optCtrl = list(maxfun = 2e5)))
```

The binary dependent variable is whether the child produced a less-transparent (1) or more-transparent (0) form of the target

verb on each trial, with all other responses excluded as missing data. The most important fixed-effect predictor is the mean adult rating (scaled and centred) for (a) less-transparent causative forms, (b) more-transparent causative forms or (c) difference scores (three separate models for each language, with the dependent variable identical in each case). We also included the interaction of this predictor by age group (4–5, 5–6) in order to investigate whether, as it appears from Figure 9–Figure 10, the adult judgement scores predict the production data of the older children better than those of the younger children (i.e., whether older children are more closely aligned with the adult standard). Prime type (reflecting whether the experimenter primed the child with a less-transparent or more-transparent causative form on the relevant trial) and verb valence (as per the binary judgment study) were included as control predictors, but as main effects only, since we have no particular predictions regarding possible interactions between these predictors and age group and/or adult ratings; and the interactions would over-complicate the model. The binary predictors of age group and prime type were coded as $-0.5/+0.5$ (effect/sum/deviation/contrast coding; as opposed to the R default of dummy/treatment/baseline coding) in order to allow them to be interpreted as “ANOVA-style” main effects.

With regard to random effects, our goal was again to strike a balance between maximal and overly complex model structures. The model did not include a random intercept for verb, since valence (already included as a main effect) is already unique for each verb. A by-verb random slope for age group was included, as it is plausible that the effect of age group differed by verb. A by-verb random slope for prime type was tried, but ultimately excluded on the basis that it explained almost no variance (i.e., the effect of prime type does not appear to differ by verb). The model included random intercepts for participant, and by-participant random slopes for (a) the adult rating (less-transparent/more-transparent/difference scores, depending on the model) and (b) prime type, as it is important to account for possible by-participant variation here (especially for the key predictor of adult rating). In the interests of parsimony, the slope-intercept correlation was not included in either case.

The models are summarized in Table 6–Table 8. Focussing on difference scores (Table 8), the adult continuous judgments are highly significantly predictive of children’s production data for all languages (with the adult difference score predictor significant at $p=0.001$ or better in each case). However, only for English ($p<0.001$) and Hebrew ($p=0.02$) was there any evidence of an interaction such that the adult continuous judgments are more predictive of older than younger children’s production data.

Interestingly, and unlike for some languages with regard to the binary judgment data, the valence predictor was never significant, except for a single model (the Hindi model predicting on the basis of more-transparent forms, and even then, only marginally so – $p=0.05$ – and with no correction for multiple comparisons).

Table 6. Production task. Mixed effects models for less-transparent forms.

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
English				
(Intercept)	-0.88	0.24	-3.75	0.000
Adult_Less_Transparent	2.87	0.23	12.35	0.000
AgeGroup1	0.61	0.35	1.74	0.081
prime_type1	-1.73	0.12	-14.88	0.000
Valence	-0.07	0.14	-0.52	0.604
Adult_Less_Transparent: AgeGroup1	2.32	0.30	7.60	0.000
Hebrew				
(Intercept)	1.20	0.28	4.31	0.000
Adult_Less_Transparent	1.01	0.25	4.01	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.07	0.19	-0.37	0.710
prime_type1	0.06	0.09	0.74	0.459
Valence	-0.20	0.24	-0.82	0.412
Adult_Less_Transparent: AgeGroup1	0.41	0.16	2.63	0.008
Hindi				
(Intercept)	-3.07	0.62	-4.92	0.000
Adult_Less_Transparent	1.80	0.62	2.91	0.004
AgeGroup1	-0.37	0.38	-0.97	0.330
prime_type1	-0.68	0.15	-4.41	0.000
Valence	-1.12	0.59	-1.90	0.058
Adult_Less_Transparent: AgeGroup1	0.49	0.34	1.45	0.148
Japanese				
(Intercept)	0.40	0.31	1.28	0.199
Adult_Less_Transparent	2.50	0.35	7.17	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.20	0.25	-0.78	0.434
prime_type1	-0.37	0.16	-2.36	0.018
Valence	-0.08	0.30	-0.27	0.787
Adult_Less_Transparent: AgeGroup1	0.13	0.26	0.49	0.627
K’iche’				
(Intercept)	2.23	0.21	10.79	0.000
Adult_Less_Transparent	0.56	0.16	3.49	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.01	0.26	-0.04	0.964
prime_type1	-0.04	0.17	-0.23	0.818
Valence	0.06	0.17	0.34	0.733
Adult_Less_Transparent: AgeGroup1	0.05	0.16	0.31	0.757

Table 7. Production task. Mixed effects models for more-transparent forms.

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
English				
(Intercept)	-0.49	0.27	-1.79	0.073
Adult_More_Transparent	-2.23	0.24	-9.30	0.000
AgeGroup1	1.09	0.36	3.02	0.003
prime_type1	-1.76	0.12	-14.54	0.000
Valence	-0.10	0.14	-0.69	0.491
Adult_More_Transparent: AgeGroup1	-1.73	0.27	-6.41	0.000
Hebrew				
(Intercept)	1.17	0.27	4.28	0.000
Adult_More_Transparent	-1.18	0.28	-4.27	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.09	0.20	-0.44	0.656
prime_type1	0.07	0.09	0.80	0.423
Valence	-0.20	0.22	-0.89	0.375
Adult_More_Transparent: AgeGroup1	-0.28	0.18	-1.56	0.119
Hindi				
(Intercept)	-2.99	0.63	-4.76	0.000
Adult_More_Transparent	-1.60	0.57	-2.81	0.005
AgeGroup1	-0.36	0.40	-0.89	0.372
prime_type1	-0.66	0.15	-4.31	0.000
Valence	-1.15	0.59	-1.96	0.050
Adult_More_Transparent: AgeGroup1	-0.24	0.23	-1.02	0.306
Japanese				
(Intercept)	0.63	0.33	1.93	0.054
Adult_More_Transparent	-2.38	0.36	-6.62	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.08	0.25	-0.33	0.739
prime_type1	-0.36	0.15	-2.36	0.018
Valence	-0.34	0.31	-1.12	0.263
Adult_More_Transparent: AgeGroup1	-0.14	0.25	-0.58	0.565
K'iche'				
(Intercept)	2.28	0.21	10.91	0.000
Adult_More_Transparent	-0.79	0.18	-4.38	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.01	0.28	-0.03	0.978
prime_type1	-0.04	0.19	-0.21	0.834
Valence	0.03	0.16	0.18	0.855
Adult_More_Transparent: AgeGroup1	0.22	0.21	1.01	0.314

Table 8. Production task. Mixed effects models for difference scores.

	<i>Est</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p(z)</i>
English				
(Intercept)	-0.69	0.20	-3.43	0.001
Adult_Difference_Score	2.85	0.20	14.61	0.000
AgeGroup1	0.93	0.32	2.90	0.004
prime_type1	-1.76	0.12	-15.02	0.000
Valence	-0.11	0.12	-0.93	0.352
Adult_Difference_Score: AgeGroup1	2.26	0.30	7.65	0.000
Hebrew				
(Intercept)	1.23	0.27	4.59	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	1.20	0.25	4.76	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.07	0.19	-0.38	0.703
prime_type1	0.06	0.09	0.74	0.458
Valence	-0.13	0.23	-0.56	0.575
Adult_Difference_Score: AgeGroup1	0.38	0.17	2.30	0.022
Hindi				
(Intercept)	-3.05	0.62	-4.94	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	1.95	0.60	3.26	0.001
AgeGroup1	-0.29	0.38	-0.75	0.455
prime_type1	-0.68	0.16	-4.41	0.000
Valence	-1.06	0.58	-1.82	0.068
Adult_Difference_Score: AgeGroup1	0.38	0.31	1.24	0.216
Japanese				
(Intercept)	0.53	0.28	1.91	0.056
Adult_Difference_Score	2.71	0.32	8.52	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.15	0.25	-0.63	0.532
prime_type1	-0.37	0.16	-2.36	0.018
Valence	-0.04	0.26	-0.14	0.891
Adult_Difference_Score: AgeGroup1	0.12	0.26	0.48	0.629
K'iche'				
(Intercept)	2.28	0.21	10.96	0.000
Adult_Difference_Score	0.71	0.17	4.27	0.000
AgeGroup1	-0.01	0.28	-0.04	0.970
prime_type1	-0.05	0.19	-0.27	0.788
Valence	0.09	0.17	0.55	0.581
Adult_Difference_Score: AgeGroup1	-0.05	0.19	-0.24	0.808

Overall, then, the production findings mirror those of the binary judgment data: As a group, children’s production data seem to reflect generally adultlike knowledge (i.e., children’s production data are very well predicted by adults’ grammaticality judgment data). Although overgeneralization errors do occur, these are relatively rare and generally restricted to a handful of verbs. Again, echoing the binary judgment data, these findings suggest that – at least from around age 4–5 – such errors reflect not so much a deficit in the grammar, but more a deficit in inhibiting the production of overgeneralized forms.

Moving on to the tests of the computational model, [Figure 11](#) plots – for English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and K’iche’ respectively – model-child correlations for (a) the full set of 60 verbs, and (b) the split-half validation test (30 verbs, randomly selected for each run), as well as the developmental pattern shown by the model for a number of example verbs (again, recall that split-half test does NOT consist of training the model on half of the participants’ grammaticality judgments; no model is ever given access to these judgments). Separate correlations are run for less-transparent and more-transparent causative forms because, although these sum to 1 for children (since all other responses are treated as missing data), the same is not true for the model which has three output units, corresponding to less-transparent, more-transparent and “Other”. That said, since the model rapidly learns to predict “Other” forms with very low probability when interrogated for a causative form, the correlations for less- and more-transparent forms are extremely similar.

For all languages except K’iche’, the model does an excellent job of predicting children’s judgment data with correlations upwards of $r=0.75$ for seen verbs, and $r=0.5$ for unseen verbs. Again, its poor performance with K’iche’ is likely attributable to difficulties with obtaining reliable corpus counts and semantic ratings ([Ambridge et al., 2020](#)). For this reason, we did not proceed to the split-half validation test for K’iche’. For the four other languages, however, the model’s ability at predicting children’s production data is on a par with its ability at predicting adults’ continuous judgment data ([Ambridge et al., 2020](#)).

The only notable shortcoming of the model is that although it simulates the overall generalization-then-retreat pattern shown by children (see [Figure 4–Figure 8](#), bottom panels), it does not simulate the observed differences between the present 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6 year olds (see [Figure 9–Figure 10](#)). That is, the model does not show an “immature” stage in which its predictions correspond more closely to the productions of the younger than the older children. This echoes the failure of the model to simulate the differences between children and adults observed in the grammatical acceptability judgment study above, and in [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#). Again, the most likely explanation seems to be that, at least by age 4–5, there is very little true overgeneralization for the model to explain. Rather, children’s grammatical knowledge in this domain is largely adultlike; they are simply somewhat less reluctant than adults to accept or produce forms that deviate from that grammar.

Discussion: Elicited production (4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6)

Data from the elicited-production task show that, children aged 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6 not only produce causative overgeneralization errors (**Someone sang / crawled / wrote / whispered / sang / slept / sat the boy*; c.f., *Someone made the boy/dog bark / sing / crawl* etc.) but do so in such a way that their by-verb patterning – except for K’iche’ – is well predicted by the computational model of [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#). At the same time, the model in its present form does not explain the retreat from overgeneralization *per se*, given that its verb-by-verb predictions are always a better fit for data from adults and older children (from [Ambridge et al., 2020](#)) than for younger children (Studies 1- and 2 above). What is the reason for this failure?

One possibility, already discussed above, is that – at least in this domain – the grammatical knowledge of 4–5-year olds is (near-) adultlike, with non-adultlike performance a consequence of extralinguistic factors. For example, reduced executive function – as compared to adults – could result in a reduced ability to resist “tempting” errors, whether in judgments or production. An alternative possibility is that these errors really do reflect a non-adultlike grammar, but that the model – in its current form – does not simulate this deficit. In order to explore this possibility, we ran a series of new models with various limitations that might correspond to those experienced by real language learners.

Study 3: Further computational modeling

Study 3 investigated the ability of a wide variety of models to simulate the binary grammatical acceptability judgment data from Study 1 (age 4;0–5;0), the elicited production data from Study 2 (ages 4;0–5;0 and 5;6–6;6) and the grammatical acceptability judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (ages 5–6, 9–10 and adults). In particular, our goal was to investigate whether, by instantiating various limitations that correspond to those facing children, it might be possible to build a model whose verb-by-verb predictions correlate *better* with the judgment and production data of younger children than those of older children and adults. If so, this constitutes preliminary evidence that children’s retreat from overgeneralization is a consequence of the reduction of the relevant limitation. If not, this constitutes further evidence that children’s retreat from overgeneralization is a consequence of changes outside of the purview of this modeling, such as increasing executive function, which allow for better rejection and inhibition of ungrammatical forms.

Because the *nnet* package does not allow for automated exploration of model parameters – which is key to the present investigation – we switched to the Deep Learning packing of *h2o.ai*, running in the R environment (see [Aiello, Eckstrand, Fu, Landry, Abouyou, 2018](#), for a tutorial). Despite its name, the Deep Learning package allows for simple connectionist architectures similar to the *nnet* networks described above (although a minimum of one hidden layer is required). The main advantage of this package for our purposes is its grid search function, which trains a model for every combination of hyperparameter values specified by the user. This allows us to rapidly explore

Figure 11. Model-child correlations for elicited production data.

possible constraints on learning that might be similar to those present for real child learners. The basic task of the *h2o* models was the same as the *nnet* models described above: to learn verb-construction mappings based on a suitable input corpus, and then generate verb-construction predictions that can then be correlated with the relevant judgment and production data from children and adults. As for the two-layer models above, the results reported below are always averaged across 48 runs of each model with different initial weights (corresponding to 48 adult/child participants per human task).

Methods

The hyperparameters explored were as follows (L1 and L2 regularization, and learning rate were all fixed at 0.01):

- **Architecture.** Two sets of models had a single hidden-unit layer, with 4 and 10 nodes respectively. Two sets of models had two hidden-unit layers, with (4,4) and (8,8) nodes respectively. Having fewer hidden units/layers reduces the ability of the model to memorize the training set (analogous to worse memory in children), forcing it to generalize more beyond the input.
- **Dropout.** Dropout also simulates memory and processing limitations in children by randomly dropping a proportion of hidden units on a given trial. It is also known to aid generalization in both models and (perhaps especially when dreaming) humans (Hoel, 2021). Two settings were used: 0 (i.e., no dropout) and 0.75.
- **Annealing.** Children’s learning starts out rapid and gradually slows, as they near the adult state. This is simulated by learning-rate annealing. Two settings were used: 0 (i.e., no annealing) and 0.75.
- **Epochs.** One obvious difference between children and adults is that the former have simply been exposed to less input. This is simulated by varying the number of epochs (each corresponding to 300,000 utterances): 2, 5, 15, and 50.

The following parameters were varied by hand:

- **Split-half.** As for the previous simulations, models were either (a) trained and tested on all 60 verbs or (b) trained on 30 verbs and tested on a held-out half, assessing their ability to generalize to unseen items (though, again, recall that verbs were never trained on human acceptability judgment or production data).
- **Semantics.** A question that remains unanswered by the previous simulations is the extent to which the models were making use of semantic similarity between verbs that tend to appear in similar constructions, as opposed to simply rote learning the training set. The equivalent question holds for children too: Although adult linguists can spot semantically based patterns, it might be that children learn verbs’ construction privileges on a verb-by-verb basis, without making semantically based generalizations. To explore this

possibility, models were either (a) trained on human-supplied semantic ratings (as above) or (b) trained on randomized semantic ratings that removed all semantic systematicity in verb+construction cooccurrences, while maintain identical architecture and an otherwise-identical training set.

- **Adult- versus child-directed speech.** The previous models used frequency obtained from adult corpora (mainly subtitle and internet corpora), simply because these were the largest available. However, it may be that the speech children hear differs systematically in important respects. To explore this possibility, training sets were based on either (a) the original adult frequency counts (of more-transparent, less-transparent and “other” forms) or (b) equivalent counts taken from child-directed speech. This was possible only for the languages with corpora available on CHILDES (MacWhinney, 2000): English, Hebrew and Japanese. In all cases, we combined all available CHILDES corpora, counting only child-directed (not child) speech. Nevertheless, the resulting combined corpora were relatively impoverished in terms of the relevant forms. For Hebrew, around 50% of verbs did not occur at all in either the more- or less-transparent causative form. For Japanese, the corresponding figure was 25%, though for the much larger English dataset, it was just 5% (three verbs: *dissolve*, *shiver* and *shrink*). Although the original child-directed corpora are much smaller than the adult-directed equivalents, the training sets were normalized, such that one epoch consists of 300,000 utterances, whether of child- or adult-directed speech. The lack of suitable child-directed corpora – and, in particular, corpora that are sufficiently dense as to capture any age-by-age variation in the relevant caregiver speech – is a limitation that should ideally be addressed in future research.

Results

The results for the models based on adult-directed corpora are summarized in Figure 12–Figure 16 (English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese, K’iche’ for all verbs), 17–21 (split-half test), 22–26 (no-semantics models, all verbs), 27–31 (no-semantics models, split-half test). The results for the models based on child-directed corpora are summarized in Figure 32–Figure 34 (English, Hebrew, Japanese, for all verbs), 35–37 (split-half test), 38–40 (no-semantics models, all verbs), 41–43 (no-semantics models, split-half test). The values shown are simple Pearson correlations between the model’s predictions and the adult/child production/judgment data labelled. The models are shown in order from best (top) to worst (bottom), according to log loss, though it is important to remember that this measure is calculated on the model’s learning of the corpus data, NOT participants’ judgment or production data, which it is never shown. Thus the “best” model in terms of log loss, is not necessarily the model that shows the highest correlation with human data (indeed, the models with lowest log-loss are at greatest risk of over-fitting the training corpora, potentially lowering their fit to human judgment and production data). Although

Figure 16. K'iche': Model-human correlations (all verbs, adult-directed corpora).

Figure 21. K'iche': Model-human correlations (split-half test, adult-directed corpora).

Figure 27. English: No-semantics-Model-human correlations (split-half test, adult-directed corpora).

Figure 38. English: No-semantics-Model-human correlations (all verbs, child-directed corpora).

Figure 41. English: No-semantics-Model-human correlations (split-half test child-directed corpora).

these figures contain a huge amount of information, the main conclusions can be summarized quite simply.

Improved overall performance. Overall, these more advanced models generally yield a better fit to the human data than do the simple two-layer models discussed above. That said, for the all-verb (c.f. split-half) models, the overall improvement is modest, and may result in part simply from the fact that so many different models were tried.

Better split-half performance. The general improvement is most noticeable for the split-half models which, for most languages, show only a small decrement compared to the all-verbs models. This is particularly the case for English (perhaps because the corpus data are so much more reliable), which showed essentially no decrement. For example, split-half English models showed correlations as high as $r=0.92$ and $r=0.93$ with 4–5 and 5–6-year olds’ production data (difference scores) versus $r=0.83$ and $r=0.90$ for the all-verbs (non-split half) models. Compared with the simpler two-layer models, then, these more advanced models do show better generalization. This suggests that human learners, too, are representing not just verbs and constructions (the input and output layers of the two-level models) but various intermediate-level abstractions (perhaps analogous to verb classes; Pinker, 1989).

More hidden units equals better performance. Although, in general, these more advanced models outperformed the previous two-layer models, some models with only a single hidden layer and/or only 4 hidden units per layer actually performed *worse* than the no-hidden-layer models (sometimes even yielding significant negative correlations with human data). This suggests that the intermediate abstractions that lie between verbs and constructions – for human learners as well as models – are complex and multifaceted (they are not, for example, simply four large verb classes). For most languages, best performance was achieved by models with two hidden layers each of 8 units, or a single hidden layer of 10 units.

Binary judgment data are messy. All models showed lower correlations with children’s binary grammaticality judgments (age 5–6) than with their production data (4–5 and 6–5) and with continuous grammaticality judgments (5–6, 9–10, adults). These findings suggest that – counter to theories that treat it as a binary construct – grammaticality is graded, and insisting on binary judgments is simply throwing away information.

Verb semantics are crucial. Removing verb semantics had a catastrophic effect on the model’s ability to generalize to unseen verbs in the split-half task, with most correlations close to zero and/or in the wrong direction. This is unsurprising, given that verb semantics is essentially the only valid basis on which the models could in principle generalize to unseen verbs. Absent semantics, the only meaningful “strategy” for the models is to over-predict the dominant response category (i.e., more-transparent or less-transparent causative form). More surprisingly, removing verb semantics also had a large deleterious effect for the all-verbs (i.e., non-split-half) models. This is surprising,

as one would have expected the models to be able to learn verbs’ preferred causative constructions simply on a lexical-verb-by-verb basis. One possible explanation is that removing semantics, and hence forcing the models to do purely lexical learning, increases over-fitting of the corpus-based training set. That is, purely lexical models learn what individual verbs just so happen to do (in terms of their construction co-occurrences), in a particular corpus. Adding semantics allows models to learn what particular (semantic) types of verbs can do, smoothing out any verb-by-verb idiosyncrasies in the particular training corpus used.

Dropout hinders, annealing is irrelevant. We experimented with a rather high level of dropout (0.75), on the basis that children’s memory and processing limitations may effectively result in the loss of many learning trials. In fact, this high level of dropout (as compared to no dropout) only hurt the models, particularly for smaller models with lower numbers of epochs, particularly on the split-half test. We also experimented with a rather high level of annealing (0.75), on the basis that children’s learning slows over time. However, at least with these values (0 versus 0.75) we did not observe any relationship between annealing and model performance.

Model performance is reassuringly consistent across architectures, human tasks and languages. Overall, we ran 2,048 different models (98,304, counting the 48 different runs of each model). A concern, therefore, is that – if we were prepared to engage in some extreme cherry-picking – we could obtain almost any results we wanted. And perhaps by focussing on the best performing models for each language, we are overexaggerating the models’ overall performance. After all, if we generated 2,048 correlation coefficients purely at random, assuming a uniform distribution, we could expect more than 100 of at least $r=0.93$ (the highest observed). Reassuringly, therefore, model performance is generally consistent in three ways: (1) Given a particular human task to predict (e.g., 4–5 year-olds’ production data), most architectures within a given language show similar performance. For example, in the first column of Figure 12, the vast majority of correlations are in the region $r=0.7–0.8$. (2) Given a particular architecture and set of hyperparameter settings (e.g., Epochs=50 Hidden layers=[4, 4], Dropout=0, Annealing=0), the model shows comparable performance across all of the adult and child datasets (e.g., first row of Figure 12). (3) Given a particular architecture and set of hyperparameter settings the model shows comparable performance across languages (except for K’iche’, for which no model ever succeeds). For example, the architecture mentioned above (e.g., Epochs=50 Hidden layers=[4, 4], Dropout=0, Annealing=0) is one of the best performing across all languages.

We failed to simulate children (including by reducing epochs or using child-directed speech). Despite running over 2,000 different models, we failed to simulate child-like performance in this domain. That is, we found no combination of tasks, architectures and (hyper/)parameter settings where the model’s predictions correlated better with any of the child measures (production, binary/graded judgments) than with adults’

graded judgments. (The only possible contender is a handful of Hebrew split-half models – $r=0.44$ for 4–5-year-old production, $r=0.25$ for adult graded judgments, but the difference is small, and probably no more than a fluke). We certainly found plenty ways to break the models, by introducing capacity, memory or processing limitations that might be akin to those shown by children. But these broken models were equally broken when it came to predicting child and adult human data. Conversely, although we stumbled across some models that predicted children’s performance better than we could have dreamed (e.g., $r=0.93$ for English 5–6-year olds’ production data), these models provided a similarly excellent fit ($r=0.85$) to adults’ graded judgment data. In particular, dramatically reducing the number of epochs to 2 or 5 (versus 15 or 50) to simulate lower levels of language exposure in young children certainly hurt model performance (particularly with high dropout and few hidden units/layers), but equally so for predicting child and adult data; it did not make the models more childlike. Similarly, basing the input sets on corpora of child-directed (versus adult-directed speech) hurt model performance (presumably because the relevant corpora are considerably smaller, and hence noisier), but equally so for predicting child and adult data.

General discussion

The question of how language learners (eventually) come to avoid the production of verb argument structure overgeneralization errors (**The clown laughed the man*) has long been seen as one that is both particularly central to acquisition research and particularly challenging (Bowerman, 1988; Pinker, 1989). Focussing on causative overgeneralization errors of this type, Ambridge *et al.* (2020) built a computational model that learns, on the basis of corpus data and human-derived verb-semantic-feature ratings, to predict adults’ by-verb preferences for less- versus more-transparent causative forms (e.g. **The clown laughed the man* vs *The clown made the man laugh*) across English, Hebrew, Hindi, Japanese and – to a lesser extent – K’iche. The aim of the present study was to investigate whether children learning these languages indeed produce such errors, and rate them as acceptable in a binary judgment task, and – if so – whether the computational model of Ambridge *et al.* (2020) can explain their patterning.

At one level, the answer to this question is a resounding “yes”. For example, English-speaking 4–5-year-olds produced errors like **Someone danced the boy* and **Someone sang the boy* (at rates of around 5% and 15% respectively), and the computational model of Ambridge *et al.* (2020) was able to predict their by-verb patterning with correlations in the region of $r=0.75$ (and $r=0.5-0.6$ for analogous errors in a binary judgment task). Similar results were observed across all languages (except K’iche), and – with a few architectural tweaks – essentially the same underlying model was able to achieve correlations as high as $r=0.8-0.9$ with human judgment and production data, even when tested on unseen verbs. These correlations are all the more remarkable when it is born in mind that the model was trained only on semantics-augmented corpus data, and was never given access to the judgment or production data against which it was benchmarked.

At a developmental level, however, the answer is “no”. Despite the introduction of numerous limitations designed to mimic those facing child language learners, no model was able to simulate development, by providing a better fit to child than adult data; or to 4–5 than 5–6 year olds’ data. Thus, while the model offers an excellent mechanistic account of how learners (eventually) acquire verbs’ argument structure preferences and restrictions, it does not in fact explain why children make errors, or how they retreat from them. Why not?

One possibility is that the “retreat from overgeneralization” is largely accomplished by age 4–5; the youngest age-group in the present study. However, this does not seem likely, given that the relevant errors are attested amongst children aged 4 years and above in (a) the present study, (b) previous experimental studies (Bidgood *et al.*, 2021; Fukuda & Fukuda, 2001), and (c) diary data (Ambridge & Ambridge, 2020; Bowerman, 1988; Nakaishi, 2016).

A second possibility, and one that we have alluded to throughout, is that children’s underlying grammatical knowledge is essentially adultlike by this age, but children are more tolerant than adults of forms that deviate from that underlying grammar, in both judgments and production. If this is the case, then the solution to the retreat from overgeneralization would lie outside of the grammar; with – for example – increasing self-confidence that allows children to judge others’ utterances as unacceptable, or improvements in executive function that allow them to inhibit their own overgeneralizations.

A third possibility, discussed by Ambridge and Ambridge (2020), is that many of children’s “overgeneralization errors” are not in fact “errors” as such, but are well matched to the child’s communicative goals; indeed, better matched than the corresponding “grammatical” form would have been. The point is best made by some examples from Ambridge and Ambridge’s (2020: 126) diary study [notes added]:

- But what does Chloe [the diarized child] mean when she says, “Can you jump me off?”, “Jump me!”, “Jump me down (the slide)!”, “Jump me up there!”? She clearly does not mean ‘Do something that indirectly causes me to instigate an internally-caused jumping action’. She means ‘Pick me up and move me upwards’. The type of causation she has in mind is single-event, direct, external causation, of almost exactly the same type that is involved in breaking a cup. In short, she doesn’t mean ‘make me jump!’ [more-transparent causative], she means ‘jump me!’ [less-transparent causative]. (p.126)
- When Chloe says, “Mermaids have got special powers; they can die baddies”, she does not have in mind indirect, two-event causation [more-transparent causative; i.e., *make X die*], but direct, single-event causation [less-transparent causative]
- It is a similar story for *dance* (“I’m dancing it”, “I can dance it”, “Your turn to dance me, Dad”). The meaning

is not ‘make me dance’ (e.g., by playing music) [more-transparent causative], but physically ‘dance me’ [less-transparent causative]. Likewise, for *eat* and *drink* (‘cause the food/liquid to go into my mouth’), *swim* (‘physically propel me through the water’), *reach* (‘lift me up’), *walk* (‘move my legs’), “go it faster”, “go[ing] them in”, *disappear* and *run*.

If this third possibility is correct, then the solution to the retreat from overgeneralization again lies outside the grammar: The reason adults don’t say things like “jump me”, “dance me” and “swim me” – and regard them as at least somewhat ungrammatical – is that adults generally do not enact single-event direct external causation on one another. And when they do these “ungrammatical” forms are allowed, or at least much improved (Ambridge & Ambridge, 2020: 126–127):

As noted by, amongst others, Pinker (1989) the adult grammar allows transitivity [i.e., less-transparent forms] that would otherwise be considered erroneous, when it is clear that the causation that the speaker has in mind is too direct to be properly conveyed by the [more-transparent] periphrastic causative; for example “when an advertisement for an amusement park says...*We’re gonna scream ya, and we’re gonna grin ya*” (Pinker, 1989, p. 348). Similarly, although *disappear* is often discussed as a prototypical example of a verb that resists transitivity, it is not uncommon to read about dictators disappearing their enemies. While you can’t normally *walk* an adult, you can walk a dog and probably even a child (at least, you can *walk her to school*); and...a baseball pitcher can walk a batter.

Given, then, its impressive correlations with adult and non-developmental child data, perhaps the present model has taken us just about as far as we can go with solutions to the retreat from overgeneralization that are confined to “the grammar”. Perhaps to go the last mile, we will have to find solutions that lie *outside* the grammar, such as the speculative possibilities discussed above.

A number of issues, however, do remain. First, despite its overall successes, the model did not significantly predict Japanese children’s binary grammaticality judgments or any of the K’iche’ data (for adults and children alike). While it is possible to come up with an apparently-reasonable explanation in each case, future work should investigate the alternative possibility that the computational model tested here perhaps does not apply universally. For Japanese binary judgments, the model’s failure is almost certainly due to a task effect, since the model does successfully predict both adults’ continuous judgments and children’s production data. For K’iche’ it is less clear. Although, as already noted, both the corpus and semantic-rating data are questionable, we should not discount the possibility that this model – and the account of causatives that it instantiates – is not well suited to languages like K’iche’ that have both transitivity and intransitivity morphological processes. For example, in English, Hebrew, Hindi and

Japanese, *laugh* is perhaps the single most prototypical example of a highly intransitive verb that strongly prefers the less-direct, more transparent causative (e.g., *Someone made the boy laugh* > **Someone laughed the boy*). Yet in K’iche’, intransitive *laugh* is derived from the transitive (though not transitive-causative) verb *laugh at*, and is – broadly speaking – acceptable in both causative forms; the same is true for *look* (derived from *look at*) and *speak* (from *speak about*). Perhaps, then, the crosslinguistic typology of causatives embodied by the computational model tested here is not quite accurate.

This relates to a second issue: While it is certainly impressive that the model can account for adult and child data across – K’iche’ aside – four unrelated languages; these four languages hardly constitute a large or representative sample of all the languages of the world. Future work using the methods here should investigate whether this model generalizes to other languages.

Third, future work using related methods should investigate whether an account of this type can explain speaker’s acquisition of verbs’ argument structure restrictions for a wide variety of syntactic and morphological constructions. We see no particular reason to believe that it cannot (e.g., see Ambridge & Blything, 2016; Li & MacWhinney, 1996, for similar models of the English *un-* prefixation and dative constructions), but, of course, the outcomes of such investigations cannot be anticipated.

Fourth, even for the restricted case of less- versus more-transparent causative forms, the model tested here does not solve the learning problem entirely, given that it starts from the point at which children have already acquired the relevant forms (e.g., the transitive-causative and *make* periphrastic causatives for English; lexical causatives and the *-(s)ase* causative marker for Japanese; the transitive and causative binyanim for Hebrew). Although the model learns a great deal about the meanings of these forms – i.e., the particular type of causation that is associated with each – the forms themselves are pre-given; and in most cases are highly abstract generalizations. In this respect, the account tested here is no different to all other accounts of this problem discussed in the Introduction. But until we have a model that can learn the generalizations in the first place, we cannot quite say that the problem of forming appropriately restricted generalizations has been solved.

Finally, the present study has important methodological implications in that three different methods – continuous grammaticality judgments, binary grammaticality judgments and elicited production – have produced findings that are generally very highly correlated with one another. Indeed, we could – at a push – argue that five different methods have converged on similar conclusions, if we include both the diary data that first uncovered such errors (e.g., Bowerman, 1988; Table 1) and the corpus analysis used to derive the model’s training data. The methodological implications are – on the one hand – that triangulating different methods on the same set of stimuli provides a particularly detailed and robust test of a particular

model; and – on the other – that where this is not possible, we can be reasonably confident that conclusions drawn on the basis of data collected using one method will generalize to another.

In conclusion, while work remains to be done to extend this research to other constructions and other language families, the present findings that the computational model developed by [Ambridge *et al.* \(2020\)](#) explains both children's binary grammaticality judgment and elicited production data across a range of languages suggest that a solution to the longstanding problem of learning verbs' argument structure restrictions – and perhaps even the retreat from overgeneralization – is within our grasp.

Data availability

Underlying data

Open Science Framework: CLASS: Cross Linguistic Acquisition of Sentence Structure. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7F2DG> ([Ambridge, 2021](#)).

This project contains the following underlying data:

AAA_CLASS_R_Analyses (Zip file containing each of the following)

BinaryJudgmentsAndProduction (Folder containing each of the following)

BinaryModeling (Folder containing each of the following)

- Binary Correlations with Old Paper.r – R code for creating the figures that correlate the present binary judgment data with the adult continuous judgment data from [Ambridge *et al.* \(2020\)](#)
- Binary Modeling.R – R code for the computational modeling.
- BRM-emot-submit.csv – Valence norms from [Warriner *et al.* \(2013\)](#)
- ENG_Adults.csv – English grammaticality judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))
- ENG_Input.csv – English input file for the computational modeling
- ENG_Results.csv – English children's binary judgment data – target for modeling
- English_Binary_Raw.csv – English children's binary judgment data – raw data
- HEB_Adults.csv – Hebrew grammaticality judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))
- HEB_Input.csv – Hebrew input file for the computational modeling
- HEB_Results.csv – Hebrew children's binary judgment data – target for modeling
- Hebrew_Binary_Raw.csv – Hebrew children's binary judgment data – raw data
- HIN_Adults.csv – Hindi grammaticality judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))
- HIN_Input.csv – Hindi input file for the computational modeling
- HIN_Results.csv – Hindi children's binary judgment data – target for modeling
- Hindi_Binary_Raw.csv – Hindi children's binary judgment data – raw data
- JAP_Adults.csv – Japanese grammaticality judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))
- JAP_Input.csv – Japanese input file for the computational modeling
- JAP_Results.csv – Japanese children's binary judgment data – target for modeling
- Japanese_Binary_Raw.csv – Japanese children's binary judgment data – raw data
- KIC_Adults.csv – Kiche' grammaticality judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))
- KIC_Input.csv – Kiche' input file for the computational modeling
- KIC_Results.csv – Kiche' children's binary judgment data – target for modeling
- Kiche_Binary_Raw.csv – K'iche' children's binary judgment data – raw data
- Tables3-4.csv – [Table 3–Table 4](#) from the present article
- Table5.csv – [Table 5](#) from the present article
- XX_Not_Included_OriginalModelArchitecture.pdf – Figure showing the architecture of the original computational model (no longer included in the paper).

ProductionModeling (Folder containing each of the following)

- BRM-emot-submit.csv – Valence norms from [Warriner *et al.* \(2013\)](#)
- ENG_4_5 – English 4-5-year-olds' raw production data
- ENG_5_6 – English 5-6-year-olds' raw production data
- ENG_Adults – English adults' judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))
- ENG_Input.csv – English input file for the computational modeling
- ENG_Results.csv – English children's production data – target for modeling
- HEB_4_5 – Hebrew 4-5-year-olds' raw production data
- HEB_5_6 – Hebrew 5-6-year-olds' raw production data
- HEB_Adults – Hebrew adults' judgment data (from [Ambridge *et al.*, 2020](#))

- HEB_Input.csv – Hebrew input file for the computational modeling
- HEB_Results.csv – Hebrew children’s production t data – target for modeling
- HIN_4_5 – Hindi 4-5-year-olds’ raw production data
- HIN_5_6 – Hindi 5-6-year-olds’ raw production data
- HIN_Adults – Hindi adults’ judgment data (from [Ambridge et al., 2020](#))
- HIN_Input.csv – Hindi input file for the computational modeling
- HIN_Results.csv – Hindi children’s production data – target for modeling
- JAP_4_5 – Japanese 4-5-year-olds’ raw production data
- JAP_5_6 – Japanese 5-6-year-olds’ raw production data
- JAP_Adults – Japanese adults’ judgment data (from [Ambridge et al., 2020](#))
- JAP_Input.csv – Japanese input file for the computational modeling
- JAP_Results.csv – Japanese children’s production data – target for modeling
- KIC_4_5 – K’iche’ 4-5-year-olds’ raw production data
- KIC_5_6 – K’iche’ 5-6-year-olds’ raw production data
- KIC_Adults – K’iche’ adults’ judgment data (from [Ambridge et al., 2020](#))
- KIC_Input.csv – Kiche’ input file for the computational modeling
- KIC_Results.csv – Kiche’ children’s production data – target for modeling
- Table8.csv – [Table 8](#) from the present article
- Tables6-7.csv – [Table 6–Table 7](#) from the present article
- V5_Production_Modeling_Environment.RData – R Environment file for original computational modeling
- Production_Correlations_with_Old_Paper.R – R code for creating the figures that correlate the present binary judgment data with the adult continuous judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#)
- V5_Production_Modeling.R – R code for original computational modeling
- English_Binary_Judge.csv – English binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- English_Cognition.csv – English adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- English_Input.csv – English Input to the computational model
- English_Production.csv – English production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Hebrew_Binary_Judge.csv – Hebrew binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Hebrew_Cognition.csv – Hebrew adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- Hebrew_Input.csv – Hebrew Input to the computational model
- Hebrew_Production.csv – Hebrew production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Hindi_Binary_Judge.csv – Hindi binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Hindi_Cognition.csv – Hindi adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- Hindi_Input.csv – Hindi Input to the computational model
- Hindi_Production.csv – Hindi production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Japanese_Binary_Judge.csv – Japanese binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Japanese_Cognition.csv – Japanese adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- Japanese_Input.csv – Japanese Input to the computational model
- Japanese_Production.csv – Japanese production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Kiche_Binary_Judge.csv – K’iche’ binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Kiche_Cognition.csv – K’iche’ adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- Kiche_Input.csv – K’iche’ Input to the computational model
- Kiche_Production.csv – K’iche’ production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- V12_Deep_Learning.R – R code to run the computational models
- V12_Just_Heatmaps.R – R code to create [Figure 12–Figure 31](#)

Figures (Folder containing [Figure 1–Figure 43](#) from the present article)

ORE_Version3 (Folder containing each of the following, relating to Study 3: Further Computational Modeling; specifically the models trained on adult-directed corpora)

ORE_Kids (Folder containing each of the following, relating to Study 3: Further Computational Modeling; specifically the models trained on child-directed corpora)

- English_Binary_Judge.csv – English binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- English_Cognition.csv – English adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- English_Input.csv – English Input to the computational model
- English_Production.csv – English production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Hebrew_Binary_Judge.csv – Hebrew binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Hebrew_Cognition.csv – Hebrew adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- Hebrew_Input.csv – Hebrew Input to the computational model
- Hebrew_Production.csv – Hebrew production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Japanese_Binary_Judge.csv – Japanese binary judgment data from the present study (target for modeling)
- Japanese_Cognition.csv – Japanese adult judgment data from [Ambridge et al. \(2020\)](#) (target for modeling)
- Japanese_Input.csv – Japanese Input to the computational model
- Japanese_Production.csv – Japanese production data from the present study (target for modeling)
- V12_Deep_Learning.R – R code to run the computational models
- V12_Just_Heatmaps.R – R code to create [Figure 32–Figure 43](#)

Extended data

Open Science Framework: CLASS: Cross Linguistic Acquisition of Sentence Structure. DOI [10.17605/OSF.IO/7F2DG](https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7F2DG) ([Ambridge, 2021](#)).

This project contains the following extended data:

- AAFinal_Sentence_Stimuli (Version 2).xlsx (Final sentence stimuli)
- **Binary grammaticality instructions1.docx (Full text of instructions given to children completing the binary judgment task)**
- Binary Judgement.zip (Zip file containing all video and audio stimuli, blank participant record and key sheets, and the sticker grid completed by children)
- Binary Judgement procedure.mp4 (Video illustrating the binary judgment procedure)
- **Practice animations.zip (Folder containing practice animations for the judgment warm up)**
- **Child instructions production.docx (Full text of instructions given to children completing the production task)**
- CausativeAnimations.zip (Zip file containing all video and audio stimuli for the production task)
- EnglishJudgmentsPsychoPy.zip (Zip file containing the PsychoPy experiment to run the judgment task).
- JudgmentLists.zip (Zip file containing the different counterbalance lists for each language)
- Production procedure.mp4 (Video illustrating the elicited production procedure)
- Prereg Production and Binary Judgments.pdf (Preregistration of the methods used)

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Zero “No rights reserved” data waiver](#) (CC0 1.0 Public domain dedication).

References

Aiello S, Eckstrand E, Fu A, et al.: *Machine Learning with R and H2O*. H2O ai. 2018.

Reference Source

Alishahi A, Stevenson S: **A computational model of early argument structure acquisition**. *Cogn Sci*. 2008; **32**(5): 789–834.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Ambridge B: **How do children restrict their linguistic generalizations? an (un-)grammaticality judgment study**. *Cogn Sci*. 2013; **37**(3): 508–543.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Ambridge B: **Argument Structure Overgeneralizations.docx**. *figshare*. Figure. 2019.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ambridge B: **Fork of CLASS: Cross Linguistic Acquisition of Sentence**

Structure. 2021.

<http://www.doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7F2DG>

Ambridge B, Ambridge C: **The retreat from transitive-causative overgeneralization errors: A review and diary study**. In Rowland, C., Theakson, A., Ambridge, B. & Twomey, K.E. *Current perspectives on child language acquisition: How children use their environment to learn*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. 2020; 113–130.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ambridge B, Blything RP: **A connectionist model of the retreat from verb argument structure overgeneralization**. *J Child Lang*. 2016; **43**(6): 1245–1276.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Ambridge B, Brandt S: **Lisa filled water into the cup: The roles of entrenchment, pre-emption and verb semantics in German speakers' L2**

- acquisition of English locatives. *Zeitschrift für Anglistik und Amerikanistik*. 2013; **61**(3): 245–263.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Barak L, Wonnacott E, et al.: **Effects of both preemption and entrenchment in the retreat from verb overgeneralization errors: Four reanalyses, an extended replication, and a meta-Analytic synthesis.** *Collabra Psychol*. 2018; **4**(1): 23.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Bidgood A, Twomey KE, et al.: **Preemption versus Entrenchment: Towards a construction-general solution to the problem of the retreat from verb argument structure overgeneralization.** *PLoS One*. 2015; **10**(4): e0123723.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Maitreyee R, Tatsumi T, et al.: **The Crosslinguistic acquisition of sentence structure: Computational modeling and grammaticality judgments from adult and child speakers of English, Japanese, Hindi, Hebrew and K'iche'.** *Cognition*. 2020; **202**: 104310.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF, et al.: **Avoiding dative overgeneralisation errors: semantics, statistics or both?** *Lang Cogn Neurosci*. 2014; **29**(2): 218–243.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF, et al.: **The roles of verb semantics, entrenchment, and morphophonology in the retreat from dative argument-structure overgeneralization errors.** *Language*. 2012a; **88**(1): 45–81.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF, et al.: **A semantics-based approach to the "no negative evidence" problem.** *Cogn Sci*. 2009; **33**(7): 1301–1316.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF: **Semantics versus statistics in the retreat from locative overgeneralization errors.** *Cognition*. 2012b; **123**(2): 260–279.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF: **Children use verb semantics to retreat from overgeneralization errors: A novel verb grammaticality judgment study.** *Cogn Linguist*. 2011; **22**(2): 303–323.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF, et al.: **The effect of verb semantic class and verb frequency (entrenchment) on children's and adults' graded judgements of argument-structure overgeneralization errors.** *Cognition*. 2008; **106**(1): 87–129.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ambridge B, Pine JM, Rowland CF, et al.: **The retreat from overgeneralization in child language acquisition: Word learning, morphology, and verb argument structure.** *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Cogn Sci*. 2013; **4**(1): 47–62.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Barak L, Goldberg AE, Stevenson S: **Comparing computational cognitive models of generalization in a language acquisition task.** *Proceedings of the 2016 conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. 2016; 96–106.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bates D, Mächler M, Bolker B, et al.: **Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models Using lme4.** *J Stat Softw*. 2015; **67**(1): 1–48.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bidgood A, Ambridge B, Pine JM, et al.: **The retreat from locative overgeneralisation errors: A novel verb grammaticality judgment study.** *PLoS One*. 2014; **9**(5): e97634.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Bidgood A, Pine J, Rowland C, et al.: **Verb argument structure overgeneralisations for the English intransitive and transitive constructions: Grammaticality judgments and production priming.** *Language and Cognition*. 2021; **13**(3): 397–437.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Blything RP, Ambridge B, Lieven EVM: **Children use statistics and semantics in the retreat from overgeneralization.** *PLoS One*. 2014; **9**(10): e110009.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Bowerman M: **The "no negative evidence" problem: how do children avoid constructing an overly general grammar?** In: Hawkins, J. A. (Ed.), *Explaining language universals*. Oxford: Blackwell. 1988; 73–101.
[Reference Source](#)
- Boyd JK, Goldberg AE: **Learning what not to say: The role of statistical preemption and categorization in a-adjective production.** *Language*. 2011; **87**(1): 55–83.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Braine MDS, Brooks PJ: **Verb argument structure and the problem of avoiding an overgeneral grammar.** In M. Tomasello, W.E. Merriman (Eds.), *Beyond names for things: Young children's acquisition of verbs*, Erlbaum, Hillsdale, NJ. 1995; 352–376.
[Reference Source](#)
- Brooks PJ, Tomasello M, Dodson K, et al.: **Young children's overgeneralizations with fixed transitivity verbs.** *Child Dev*. 1999; **70**(6): 1325–1337.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Brooks PJ, Zizak O: **Does preemption help children learn verb transitivity?** *J Child Lang*. 2002; **29**(4): 759–781.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fukuda S, Fukuda SE: **The acquisition of complex predicates in Japanese specifically language-impaired and normally developing children.** *Brain Lang*. 2001; **77**(3): 305–320.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Goldberg AE: **Constructions: A construction grammar approach to argument structure.** University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1995.
[Reference Source](#)
- Goldberg AE: **Corpus evidence of the viability of statistical preemption.** *Cogn Linguist*. 2011; **22**(1): 131–153.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Goldberg AE: **Explain Me This.** Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2019.
[Reference Source](#)
- Gropen J, Pinker S, Hollander M, et al.: **Affectedness and Direct Objects: the Role of Lexical Semantics in the Acquisition of Verb Argument Structure.** *Cognition*. 1991; **41**(1–3): 153–195.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Harmon Z, Kapatsinski V: **Putting old tools to novel uses: The role of form accessibility in semantic extension.** *Cogn Psychol*. 2017; **98**: 22–44.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hoel E: **The overfitted brain: Dreams evolved to assist generalization.** *Patterns (N Y)*. 2021; **2**(5): 100244.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Hsu AS, Chater N: **The logical problem of language acquisition: A probabilistic perspective.** *Cogn Sci*. 2010; **34**(6): 972–1016.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hsu AS, Horng A, Griffiths TL, et al.: **When absence of evidence is evidence of absence: Rational inferences from absent data.** *Cogn Sci*. 2017; **41** Suppl 5: 1155–1167.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Irani A: **How Children learn to disappear causative errors.** In M.M. Brown and B. Dailey (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 43rd Boston University Conference on Language Development*. Somerville, MA: Cascadia Press, 2009; 298–310.
[Reference Source](#)
- Kapatsinski V, Olejarczuk P, Redford MA: **Perceptual Learning of Intonation Contour Categories in Adults and 9- to 11-Year-Old Children: Adults Are More Narrow-Minded.** *Cogn Sci*. 2017; **41**(2): 383–415.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Kuznetsova A, Brockhoff PB, Christensen RHB: **ImerTest Package: Tests in Linear Mixed Effects Models.** *J Stat Softw*. 2017; **82**(13): 1–26.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Li P, MacWhinney B: **Cryptotype, overgeneralization and competition: A connectionist model of the learning of English reversible prefixes.** *Conn Sci*. 1996; **8**(1): 3–30.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- MacWhinney B: **The CHILDES Project: Tools for analyzing talk.** Third Edition. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. 2000; 26(4): 657.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Nakaishi Y: **The errors of Transitive and Intransitive Verbs by Two Japanese L1 Children [nihongo wo bogo to suru ni yooji no jidooshi tadooshi no goyoo].** Bulletin of the Faculty of Human Culture and Science, Prefectural University of Hiroshima. 2016; **11**: 75–85.
- Peirce J, Gray JR, Simpson S, et al.: **PsychoPy2: Experiments in behavior made easy.** *Behav Res Methods*. 2019; **51**(1): 195–203.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Perek F, Goldberg AE: **Linguistic generalization on the basis of function and constraints on the basis of statistical preemption.** *Cognition*. 2017; **168**: 276–293.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Perfors A, Tenenbaum JB, Wonnacott E: **Variability, negative evidence, and the acquisition of verb argument constructions.** *J Child Lang*. 2010; **37**(3): 607–642.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Pinker S: **Learnability and Cognition: The acquisition of argument structure.** Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1989.
[Reference Source](#)
- R Core Team: **R: A language and environment for statistical computing.** R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
- Robenalt C, Goldberg AE: **Judgment evidence for statistical preemption: It is relatively better to vanish than to disappear a rabbit, but a lifeguard can equally well backstroke or swim children to shore.** *Cogn Linguist*. 2015; **26**(3): 467–503.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Robenalt C, Goldberg AE: **Nonnative speakers do not take competing alternative expressions into account the way native speakers do.** *Lang Learn*. 2016; **66**(1): 60–93.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Shibatani M, Pardeshi P: **The causative continuum.** M. Shibatani (Ed.), *The grammar of causation and interpersonal manipulation*. John Benjamins, Amsterdam. 2002; 85–126.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Smith CS: **Jespersen's 'move and change' class and causative verbs in**

English. Linguistic and literary studies in honor of Archibald A. Hill. Volume II. Descriptive linguistics. Eds. Mohammad A. Jazayery et al. The Hague: Mouton. 1970; 101–109.

Stefanowitsch A: **Negative entrenchment: A usage-based approach to negative evidence.** *Cogn Linguist.* 2008; **19**(3): 513–531.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Theakston AL: **The role of entrenchment in children's and adults' performance on grammaticality judgment tasks.** *Cognitive Development.* 2004; **19**(1): 15–34.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Twomey K, Chang F, Ambridge B: **Do as I say, not as I do: A lexical distributional account of English locative verb class acquisition.** *Cogn Psychol.* 2014; **73**: 41–71.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Twomey KE, Chang F, Ambridge B: **Lexical distributional cues, but not situational cues, are readily used to learn abstract locative verb-structure associations.** *Cognition.* 2016; **153**: 124–139.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Venables WN, Ripley BD: **Modern Applied Statistics with S.** Fourth edition. Springer, New York. 2002.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Warriner AB, Kuperman V, Brysbaert M: **Norms of valence, arousal, and dominance for 13,915 English lemmas.** *Behav Res Methods.* 2013; **45**(4): 1191–1207.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Wickham H: **ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis.** Springer-Verlag New York. 2016.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Wicherts JM, Veldkamp CL, Augusteijn HE, et al.: **Degrees of freedom in planning, running, analyzing, and reporting psychological studies: A checklist to avoid p-hacking.** *Front Psychol.* 2016; **7**: 1832.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Wonnacott E, Newport EL, Tanenhaus MK: **Acquiring and processing verb argument structure: Distributional learning in a miniature language.** *Cogn Psychol.* 2008; **56**(3): 165–209.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

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Version 2

Reviewer Report 14 February 2022

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Vsevolod Kapatsinski

Department of Linguistics, University of Oregon, Eugene, OR, USA

This revision has admirably addressed my concerns. I appreciate the careful exploration of the space of model parameters that might account for retreat from overgeneralization.

My one concern is that the authors might now be overly pessimistic about the ability of their model to capture the developmental change because a linear correlation with binarized/categorical data will always be lower than with an underlying continuous variable. Consider the following simulation:

```
nReps<-1000
nKids=32
cor.sample.continuous<-rep(0,nReps)
cor.sample.binary<-rep(0,nReps)
for (i in 1:nReps)
{
  prediction<-rnorm(mean=0,sd=1,n=nKids)
  rating<-prediction*.7+rnorm(mean=0,sd=.3,n=nKids)
  cor.sample.continuous[i]<-cor(prediction,rating)
  binary.rating<-rep(0,nKids)
  binary.rating[which(rating>0)]<-1
  cor.sample.binary[i]<-cor(prediction,binary.rating)
}
length(which(cor.sample.continuous>cor.sample.binary)) #continuous correlation always higher
than binary in my run
hist(cor.sample.continuous-cor.sample.binary)
```

The authors note that binary judgments are messy compared to production (something we have also consistently observed in my lab). However, even production data are categorical: the speaker has to make a choice of what to produce, and if they maximize they will always choose the more acceptable option, even if the acceptability difference is small. So I think the loss of information

that comes from turning continuous variables categorical might still explain the advantage of the model on the continuous adult data here.

I would have also liked to see graphs that show the points that follow Figure 43 (showing model fit as a function of these parameters and maybe even a confidence region for a non-parametric regression thereof), and relegated Figs 12-43 to an appendix. It is rather hard to extract the patterns or evaluate their reliability across the huge number of tables.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My research deals with the role of domain-general learning mechanisms in language acquisition.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 25 January 2022

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Lisa Pearl

Language Science, University of California, Irvine, Irvine, CA, USA

I like to sign my reviews when possible. ~~Lisa S. Pearl

I think this revision has done a fine job addressing the comments that occurred to me during my reading of the previous manuscript version. I also really appreciate the motivation and implementation of Study 3, which I mention in the more-detailed comments below. Because the revision did such a fine job addressing my previous comments, I was then able to notice things in this current version that I don't believe I noticed before (summarized below). All my current comments are basically suggestions for potential clarifications, especially a conceptual one involving what counts as being "part of the grammar" vs. not. I definitely support the indexing of this manuscript, though I do think it would be improved by incorporating some text that responds to the comments I raise below.

Specific comments:

1. What's part of the grammar

When we start looking at results from the behavioral work (e.g., in Study 1), it's the "difference" scores (the relative rate of less- vs. more-transparent forms) that we get the best results from. Given this, it may be helpful to talk about the adult-like "knowledge" children seem to have as the rate at which one form is preferred over another, given what Figure 3 is plotting. This finding is contrasted with children's individual judgments of less- or more-transparent forms, which may "deviate from the underlying grammar". So, here,

“grammar” is about the relative rate on a verb-by-verb basis, rather than the acceptability of any particular form.

To play devil’s advocate, I could imagine someone thinking that the underlying grammar would also include the knowledge of individual verb form’s acceptability (e.g., that “Someone broke it” and “Someone made it break” are both pretty acceptable, even if one is used more than another). This issue of what’s part of the grammar vs. not comes up again when you discuss why children seem to over-accept forms that adults find less acceptable – you suggest one explanation is simply metacognition immaturity (i.e., something like developing process abilities, rather than developing knowledge), because children’s “grammatical knowledge” is essentially adultlike. “Adult-like” is true for the rate of form use, but not obviously so for the acceptability of a particular form for a specific verb.

In a related vein, in the general discussion, you mention the possibility that children are sensitive to the internal-causation vs. external-causation meanings associated with the more- and less-transparent forms (which I love!), and you talk about this sensitivity as something outside the grammar. Playing devil’s advocate again, is it obviously outside the grammar?

That is, isn’t it still something about the language (and so about the language’s grammar) to learn which precise semantic meanings are allowed to be implemented in the language with the appropriate syntactic forms? The learnability issue then reminds me of the problem in lexical acquisition, where children need to learn which concepts are lexicalized with single words in their language.

More generally, this issue of being part of (i.e., inside) vs. outside the grammar may be something that gets clarified by an earlier explicit discussion of what’s considered “grammar” vs. not, and why (e.g., the rate of less-transparent vs. more-transparent forms vs. a specific form for a specific verb being more vs. less acceptable). If what’s considered “grammar” is clarified there, it may be easier to refer back to whatever distinction in the general discussion when you delve into the third possible explanation about children overgeneralizing with respect to the mapping between causation semantics and causative forms.

2. Introduction, the verb-semantics hypothesis

It seems that the verb-semantics hypothesis isn’t really a learning mechanism *per se*, as described, in contrast to the other two statistical approaches. Instead, verb semantics seems more like a feature that would be used in a learning mechanism – for instance, the mechanism would be that the learner recognizes the relevant semantic feature and then learns to map its various values (internal-causation vs. external-causation) to the appropriate forms (i.e., internal causation = more-transparent periphrastic vs. external-causation = less-transparent transitive in English). It may be useful to briefly note this when you introduce these three approaches, especially because your modeling work will use the semantic feature approach and embed it in a specific type of statistical learning mechanism via the computational model.

3. Introduction, discussion of previous Ambridge et al. 2020 model

It may be helpful to explicitly connect the implementation of this model to the mechanisms

you just introduced from prior approaches (i.e., preemption, entrenchment, verb semantics). In particular, the learning based on relevant input frequencies captures preemption, since preemption depends on relative input frequencies; having an “OTHER” node for utterances that don’t use either of the causative forms relates to entrenchment, since the total frequency of the verb usage (across all forms) matters; the input contains four “semantics” units, which captures the verb-semantics hypothesis.

4. Study 1 results, where valence for Japanese and Ki’che’ matters more, in particular that the more-transparent form is preferred when there’s negative valence because the more-transparent form suggests unintentionally.

To me, this seems like a really interesting finding about the (potential) relationship between (un)intentionality, causative form, and valence. I wonder if this is something that might somehow be incorporated into future modeling work – that is, that the forms themselves (more- vs. less-transparent) would be associated with specific semantic features, rather than only the verbs being associated with semantic features. The idea that forms could be associated with semantic features comes back again when we think about the distinction of internal-causation vs. external-causation.

5. Study 3

I think Study 3 is a really valuable contribution, with the goal of building processing limitations into the computational model, in order to try to capture some of the actual learning effects (i.e., what would cause the retreat from overgeneralization, if it actually hasn’t already occurred by age four). More generally, even if the over-acceptance of individual forms (either the less-transparent or the more-transparent) is due to some kind of immature processing, rather than immature knowledge of what’s acceptable, it seems like that could be captured in a model that also has immature processing, implemented in whatever way makes the most sense. And then, we would have a better idea about potential explanations for what the immature processing actually is in children that generates the observed behavior in the experiments (i.e., related to the immature processing implementations in the model vs. something else, like the executive function maturation suggested at various points).

6. The model in Study 3

It might be helpful to note which option in these model parameter explorations you consider to be more child-like/immature processing – you do this for dropout, but you can probably just hammer it home in each case. For instance, in the case of the architecture, would it be having 1 hidden layer, since that represents a cognitive bottleneck (forcing more generalization)? (It may also help to mention some interpretation of what hidden layers could represent, as you do in your results discussion: they correspond to intermediate representations above the individual verb level.) For dropout, the 0.75 dropout is more child-like/immature; for annealing, .75 = starting out by exploring lots of possibilities – even less probable ones – and then becoming more conservative over time is (which means exploring only the more probable possibilities); this is more child-like/immature because there’s actual maturation of the “conservativity” in exploration. For the epochs, having fewer epochs means less data exposure, which is more child-like/immature. In the case of the epoch limitation, you may want to note that this is less a processing limitation, and instead a simple experience (input quantity) limitation.

7. Organizational suggestion for results of study 3

It's brilliant to have all the results available in Tables 12-43, but as you note in the text itself, the information is a little overwhelming, and can be summarized pretty simply. Maybe it's better to have these in an appendix instead, so as not to break up the flow of the text so much?

8. Study 3 interpretation and limitation for model exploration with respect to dropout and annealing

It might be helpful to mention that you only looked at one value for each of these (0.75 = severe dropoff and major annealing), and of course other values might have different effects. But this is for future work, if we believe that these parameters capture useful potential aspects of immature processing (in particular, immature memory/attention for dropout and immature "conservativity" for annealing).

9. General discussion, executive function as potential future modeling work

I wonder if the executive function aspect could be incorporated into a future computational model. The way the process is described here, it would be a two-step model: step 1 is the learning process implemented in the current model to produce the probability of an output form for a given verb, and step 2 is an additional layer that controls actual output (how much inhibition there is for a generalization). If something like this is what you have in mind, it could be worth mentioning as a concrete future work possibility.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Computational cognitive models of language development.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 14 May 2021

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Lisa Pearl

Language Science, University of California, Irvine, Irvine, CA, USA

I like to sign my reviews when possible. ~~Lisa S. Pearl

I think this manuscript makes great contributions in terms of addressing an interesting theoretical question about language acquisition: why children overgeneralize certain verb forms and how

they recover from that overgeneralization. Moreover, the authors use multiple methods and look at data from multiple unrelated languages to assess the generalizability of their conclusions, and are pretty clear about the limitations of their current findings. As a computational cognitive modeler focusing on language acquisition, I especially appreciate the difficulties that go into (i) designing a computational model that connects concretely to empirical acquisition data, and (ii) interpreting model results in a cognitively-meaningful way. Because of this, I found myself deeply interested in what I would consider relevant modeling details, and unfortunately a bit confused by some of the main takeaways without those details. If possible, I'd love to see a revision that included some of that information, focusing on the aspects I mention in more detail below. Besides this, I had a few other specific thoughts that I discuss below.

(1) The model

(a) Model input, especially for children of different ages

It seems important to use input data distributions from children of the ages intended to be modeled (4;0-5;0, 5;6-6;6), as it's possible that input frequencies (particularly for uses of individual lexical items) would shift as children get older. Relatedly, children's perception of the relevant semantic properties may also be developing over time -- right now, adult data are used as a standin because that's the empirical data available (which is really great to have!). But that, along with the changing input frequencies, might explain why the model doesn't capture younger (immature) child behavior.

More generally, to capture children's knowledge at different ages with the kind of incremental model you have, I think you'd want to start the model off with some base level of knowledge (the equivalent of an informed Bayesian prior) that corresponds to what a child of that age is meant to know. For instance, if you wanted to pursue this idea, I could imagine running the model for the 4;0-5;0 child data, and then using that end state of that model as the start state for running the 5;6-6;6 child data (assuming the input frequency data actually differed between these two groups).

I don't think the current manuscript needs to do this, but I think it's worth discussing as a potential limitation and/or future work.

(b) Model implementation

(i) The manuscript notes that the model used is the very same one implemented by Ambridge *et al.* 2020, but it would be helpful just to give a very basic sketch of some of the finer details when it's first presented (e.g., how many input units are there, where the input data come from, etc.)

More generally, given the explanatory goals you have with the input features you're using, I'm curious about them motivation for using a neural network, rather than a more transparent classifier (like SVM, logistic regression) or cognitive model (like Bayesian inference). It seems like a more-transparent modeling methodology would speak to the goal of how predictive/explanatory the hypothesized features are. Of course, I realize you've already developed the model in the Ambridge *et al.* 2020 previous work, and want to test it here. But I do wonder if the explanatory goal would have been better-served by a different modeling choice. Perhaps the model incorporates information in a distributed way (e.g., like current word embedding approaches like GloVe or RoBERTa do), and these input representations would be hard to replicate in a different modeling type? At any rate, I do think a little more background on the modeling choice might be helpful somewhere in this paper for readers like me.

(ii) Split-half validation: I think it's good to see the split-half validation, even if you couldn't do it for K'iche' in Study 2. The results from split-half validation are much more believable, as opposed to the test-on-training when you use the full 60. That is, the split-validation captures what the model has learned more generally rather than what the model has learned (and potentially overfit) for these data. I know the full-60 correlations have higher values, but the split-half validation is more credible for the interesting explanatory claims you want to make about input frequency and the semantic features. Because of this, I'd be careful about playing up the full-60 modeling results compared with the split-half validation.

(iii) The discussion currently says about the modeling approach: "Given that an identical model can predict...without having been trained on any of these datasets". I think I may have misunderstood something fundamental about the model then (and this may make my previous comments about the full-60 vs. split-half validation make less sense). I thought the model, as a neural net, gets trained to predict the correct output value on the basis of the input, and is given pairs of input-output to learn from over time. So, because the model has seen all 60 verbs (for the full-60 models) or 30 (for the split-half validation models), the model has in fact been trained (for the full-60) or partially trained (for the split-half) on these datasets.

If this isn't right, then I think the manuscript would definitely benefit from more description of the model itself and how it was trained, since this seems like a really important aspect of what you want to say in the general discussion. To me, the key idea is that certain aspects of the input have great explanatory power (with r around 0.5): the input frequencies of the forms, and the four semantic features. With these viewed as the relevant part of the input, a modeled learner can both overgeneralize and retreat from overgeneralization.

(c) *What the model is meant to do*: Related to the previous point, I think it may be helpful to draw out the explanatory power more of the frequency and semantic factors you investigate. If I'm understanding the goal of the modeling correctly, that's really what the model is meant to do: predict when overgeneralization does and doesn't happen, on the basis of these factors.

(2) What counts as overgeneralization

(i) When I was looking at Figure 3, I had a minor point of confusion about what counts as an overgeneralization. Overgeneralizations are defined as items where kids use the forms more equally than adults (i.e., kids think the forms are less different than adults). But, why not focus on the more natural overgeneralizations for the causative, where adults prefer the more-transparent ("A made B VERB") over the less-transparent ("A VERBed B") form more so than children do?

In Hindi for example, it seems like overgeneralizations also include items where adults prefer the less-transparent ("A VERBed B") over the more-transparent, because the adult difference score is positive.

(ii) Study 2:

The current manuscript suggests that less-transparent forms ("A VERBed B") are more frequent in children's input, and that's why children use the less-transparent forms more than adults. Is the input difference in general for causative verbs, or just for individual verbs? That is, is the less-transparent more common for causative verbs as a whole, and that's what you think is causing the overgeneralization here? If so, then it means children have grouped together "causative verbs" as

a class, and are tracking frequencies about that class.

If instead you mean that less-transparent forms are more common for individual verbs, then do you mean that “overgeneralization” (as defined here by using the less-transparent form more often than adults) is simply driven by the input? That is, it’s just a reflection of an input that supports overgeneralizations, when defined as using the less-transparent form more often than you should. (Side note: This seems a little different from allowing a form that adults categorically think is not allowed. It might be helpful to note this.)

Followup if you meant children’s input has more less-transparent uses for individual verbs: Is this something you could test for explicitly, by just seeing how well input frequency accounts for child judgments, and not including the 4 semantic features?

(3) Very minor thing: Figure resolution

Several figures in my pdf of the manuscript were rather fuzzy -- figures 1-3, an 9-11. It would be good to get better resolution versions of these.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Computational cognitive models of language development.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 07 Jan 2022

Ben Ambridge, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK

We thank this reviewer for their very helpful comments. In particular, the prompt to investigate the extent to which the model can explain the *retreat* from overgeneralization developmentally inspired new modeling work that caused us to rethink exactly what the model is telling us. Reviewer comments in italics.

I think this manuscript makes great contributions in terms of addressing an interesting theoretical question about language acquisition: why children overgeneralize certain verb forms and how they recover from that overgeneralization. Moreover, the authors use multiple methods and look at data from multiple unrelated languages to assess the generalizability of their conclusions, and are pretty clear about the limitations of their current findings. As a computational cognitive modeler focusing on language acquisition, I especially appreciate the difficulties that go into (i) designing a computational model that connects concretely to empirical acquisition data, and (ii) interpreting model results in a cognitively-meaningful way. Because of this, I found myself deeply interested in what I would consider relevant modeling details, and unfortunately a bit confused by some of the main takeaways without those details. If possible, I'd love to see a revision that included some of that information, focusing on the aspects I mention in more detail below. Besides this, I had a few other specific thoughts that I discuss below.

(1) The model

(a) Model input, especially for children of different ages

It seems important to use input data distributions from children of the ages intended to be modeled (4;0-5;0, 5;6-6;6), as it's possible that input frequencies (particularly for uses of individual lexical items) would shift as children get older. Relatedly, children's perception of the relevant semantic properties may also be developing over time -- right now, adult data are used as a standin because that's the empirical data available (which is really great to have!). But that, along with the changing input frequencies, might explain why the model doesn't capture younger (immature) child behavior.

Author Response: We have now included an "Adult- versus Child-directed speech" manipulation (see subheading of this name) for English, Hebrew and Japanese (no suitable corpora were available for Hindi and K'iche'). We would certainly agree that children's semantic knowledge is unlikely to be adultlike, so in the absence of semantic rating data from children we now include ("Study 3: Further computational modeling") no-semantics models in which this information is removed, to investigate whether it is possible to learn these restrictions in a purely lexical way. Other manipulations in this new modeling section are also indicative here, including "dropout" which simulates – amongst other things – missing or incomplete semantic information.

More generally, to capture children's knowledge at different ages with the kind of incremental model you have, I think you'd want to start the model off with some base level of knowledge (the equivalent of an informed Bayesian prior) that corresponds to what a child of that age is meant to know. For instance, if you wanted to pursue this idea, I could imagine running the model for the 4;0-5;0 child data, and then using that end state of that model as the start state for running the 5;6-6;6 child data (assuming the input frequency data actually differed between these two groups).

I don't think the current manuscript needs to do this, but I think it's worth discussing as a potential limitation and/or future work.

Author Response: We have added child-directed counts where we can but, as we note, these corpora are very small and so “were relatively impoverished in terms of the relevant forms”; And even this is collapsing across ALL available speech to children in the relevant language, regardless of age. So we have adopted R3’s suggestion of noting that “The lack of suitable child-directed corpora – and, in particular, corpora that are sufficiently dense as to capture any age-by-age variation in the relevant caregiver speech – is a limitation that should ideally be addressed in future research”

(b) Model implementation

(i) The manuscript notes that the model used is the very same one implemented by Ambridge et al. 2020, but it would be helpful just to give a very basic sketch of some of the finer details when it’s first presented (e.g., how many input units are there, where the input data come from, etc.)

Author Response: We have now added detail of this modeling (see section “Because we adopt the same model...”), and have now added a new modeling section (Study 3) in which we formally experiment with parameter settings.

More generally, given the explanatory goals you have with the input features you’re using, I’m curious about them motivation for using a neural network, rather than a more transparent classifier (like SVM, logistic regression) or cognitive model (like Bayesian inference). It seems like a more-transparent modeling methodology would speak to the goal of how predictive/explanatory the hypothesized features are. Of course, I realize you’ve already developed the model in the Ambridge et al. 2020 previous work, and want to test it here. But I do wonder if the explanatory goal would have been better-served by a different modeling choice. Perhaps the model incorporates information in a distributed way (e.g., like current word embedding approaches like GloVe or RoBERTa do), and these input representations would be hard to replicate in a different modeling type? At any rate, I do think a little more background on the modeling choice might be helpful somewhere in this paper for readers like me.

Author Response: The additional information about the modeling should hopefully make this clear. In particular, the reason we chose this methodology is because we believe that it best maps onto the task facing learners (although of course, no model is a perfect match). In production, learners have a message to convey (including causation or not) which includes the relevant caused event/verb (and the detailed semantic features of it), and must choose a construction to convey it. Of course, this is a vast oversimplification. But alternative tasks like Bayesian clustering, in our view, map less well onto this real-world learning scenario. Our main goal is not so much to pick apart different hypothesized features (e.g., semantics, entrenchment, preemption) but – almost the opposite – to show how these fall naturally out of a psychologically-plausible learning mechanism. That said, we do now pick apart the effects of semantics and lexical learning by running models in which the semantic information is removed. These demonstrate that the semantics is crucial to learning, and particularly in generalizing to novel verbs (see next comment).

(ii) Split-half validation: I think it’s good to see the split-half validation, even if you couldn’t do it for K’iche’ in Study 2. The results from split-half validation are much more believable, as opposed to the test-on-training when you use the full 60. That is, the split-validation captures what the model has learned more generally rather than what the model has learned (and potentially overfit) for these data. I know the full-60 correlations have higher values, but the split-half validation is more credible for the interesting explanatory claims you want to make about input

frequency and the semantic features. Because of this, I'd be careful about playing up the full-60 modeling results compared with the split-half validation.

Author Response: This does seem to reflect – as per the next comment – a miscommunication on our part about how the split-half test works...

(iii) The discussion currently says about the modeling approach: "Given that an identical model can predict...without having been trained on any of these datasets". I think I may have misunderstood something fundamental about the model then (and this may make my previous comments about the full-60 vs. split-half validation make less sense). I thought the model, as a neural net, gets trained to predict the correct output value on the basis of the input, and is given pairs of input-output to learn from over time. So, because the model has seen all 60 verbs (for the full-60 models) or 30 (for the split-half validation models), the model has in fact been trained (for the full-60) or partially trained (for the split-half) on these datasets.

Author Response: As we now make explicit "note that this "split half validation" did NOT consist of training the model on half of the participants' grammaticality judgments and having it predict the held-out half. Rather, it consisted of withholding half of the verbs from the corpus-derived training set, before interrogating it for its predictions for the held-out verbs". We also give a similar reminder whenever we discuss the split-half test.

If this isn't right, then I think the manuscript would definitely benefit from more description of the model itself and how it was trained, since this seems like a really important aspect of what you want to say in the general discussion. To me, the key idea is that certain aspects of the input have great explanatory power (with r around 0.5): the input frequencies of the forms, and the four semantic features. With these viewed as the relevant part of the input, a modeled learner can both overgeneralize and retreat from overgeneralization.

Author Response: Yes, we have now added a great deal more information about the model's training; both for the original model (see above) and the new expanded modeling work(Study 3).

(c) What the model is meant to do: Related to the previous point, I think it may be helpful to draw out the explanatory power more of the frequency and semantic factors you investigate. If I'm understanding the goal of the modeling correctly, that's really what the model is meant to do: predict when overgeneralization does and doesn't happen, on the basis of these factors.

Author Response: Yes, this is now made explicit in the section "Verb semantics are crucial. "

(2) What counts as overgeneralization

(i) When I was looking at Figure 3, I had a minor point of confusion about what counts as an overgeneralization. Overgeneralizations are defined as items where kids use the forms more equally than adults (i.e., kids think the forms are less different than adults). But, why not focus on the more natural overgeneralizations for the causative, where adults prefer the more-transparent ("A made B VERB") over the less-transparent ("A VERBed B") form more so than children do? In Hindi for example, it seems like overgeneralizations also include items where adults prefer the less-transparent ("A VERBed B") over the more-transparent, because the adult difference score is positive.

Author Response: Sorry, this was due to confusing colour choices in Figure 3, which originally went from red (+2) to green (-2). We agree with R3 that Overgeneralizations occur in both directions, so now +2 and -2 are both red, grading into green at the midpoint (zero).

So (perfect) green indicates that children's preference for the more-over less transparent form (or vice versa) is the same as adults (i.e., zero degree of overgeneralization). Having red for maximal overgeneralizations in both directions sounds confusing at first, but it is more intuitive when combined with the position of the verbs on the plot: Red items on the left of the plot mean that children's preference for the less over more transparent form is smaller than it should be (e.g., English children fail to sufficiently dislike Someone danced the boy as compared to Someone made the boy dance). Red items on the right of the plot means that children's preference for the more over less transparent form is smaller than it should be (e.g., English children fail to sufficiently dislike Someone made the room decorate as compared to Someone decorated the room). We also changed the colour scheme for Figures 1-2 to avoid suggesting incorrectly that Figures 1-2 and Figure 3 are comparable with regard to colour coding.

(ii) Study 2:

The current manuscript suggests that less-transparent forms ("A VERBed B") are more frequent in children's input, and that's why children use the less-transparent forms more than adults. Is the input difference in general for causative verbs, or just for individual verbs? That is, is the less-transparent more common for causative verbs as a whole, and that's what you think is causing the overgeneralization here? If so, then it means children have grouped together "causative verbs" as a class, and are tracking frequencies about that class. If instead you mean that less-transparent forms are more common for individual verbs, then do you mean that "overgeneralization" (as defined here by using the less-transparent form more often than adults) is simply driven by the input? That is, it's just a reflection of an input that supports overgeneralizations, when defined as using the less-transparent form more often than you should. (Side note: This seems a little different from allowing a form that adults categorically think is not allowed. It might be helpful to note this.)

Author Response: We have removed this section because further detailed investigation of our results, including via the new modeling, suggests that although the model correlates well with both child and adult data, it does not actually simulate specific verb-by-verb patterns in the retreat from overgeneralization.

Follow up if you meant children's input has more less-transparent uses for individual verbs: Is this something you could test for explicitly, by just seeing how well input frequency accounts for child judgments, and not including the 4 semantic features?

Author Response :Yes, we have now investigated this (again see section "Verb semantics are crucial").

(3) Very minor thing: Figure resolution

Several figures in my pdf of the manuscript were rather fuzzy -- figures 1-3, an 9-11. It would be good to get better resolution versions of these.

Author Response: Yes, we have now supplied these as PDFs instead which should address the issue.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 04 May 2021

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.14078.r26710>

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Vsevolod Kapatsinski

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This article reports novel data on overgeneralization, a core topic in the acquisition of language. It expands a prior study by the researchers to a younger age range. An important strength of this paper is the cross-linguistic breadth of the investigation, which is unprecedented except for the paper's companion piece (Ambridge *et al.*, 2020). The main weakness of the paper is that the authors do not show that their computational model can account for the developmental trajectory. This is important because the main claim of the paper is that the model provides an account of *retreat* from overgeneralization. A second, related weakness of the analyses is that the authors say very little about how performance changes with age. Third, assuming that the model does account for the developmental trajectory, it would be important to show *why* it does. I elaborate on these issues below.

Major points:

1. What properties of the computational model are important to account for the behavior?

The computational model used in this paper is a simple two-layer connectionist network, in which the input consists of a local (one-hot) encoding of verb identity, and 4 continuous semantic parameters thought to be relevant to the choice between the causative constructions. Based on the preceding paper by the authors (Ambridge *et al.*, 2020), the model also has an input node that represents whether the input is causative. The existence of this node is likely crucial for predicting that the more frequent causative construction will be overgeneralized, until the associations of specific semantic and lexical cues strengthen enough to override this initial bias. The output layer consists of three nodes for direct causative, indirect causative and 'other'. The learning rule is not described here, but is said to be a variant of Widrow-Hoff in Ambridge *et al.* (2020). It seems likely that the discriminative nature of this learning rule is crucial for the performance of the model, but this is not shown or discussed. It is also possible that a simple Hebbian learning rule would also do.

It is important to provide a full description of the model here so that the work could be replicated, and the paper could be read as a stand-alone piece. A full description should include: the learning rule, the activation function on the output node, learning rate, and any other parameters that were set. The authors also need to describe whether they have attempted to use different learning rules, activation functions, or parameter settings. Such explorations would be very informative for determining what properties of the model are responsible for its ability to explain the human behavior. In particular, does it matter that the learning rule is discriminative?

2. How does the behavior change with age?

It is not clear how the behavior in question changes with age. There are several possibilities, none of which are mutually exclusive. First, it could be that the children are more accepting of deviation from prior experience than adults (e.g., Kapatsinski *et al.*, 2017)¹. It could also be that children are gradually picking up on the semantic predictors conditioning the choice of the construction (Goldberg, 2019). Finally, it is also possible that, with age, children become more confident in their estimates of how individual verbs behave (e.g., suggested by Erker & Guy, 2012)². Without knowing what changes with age, we cannot tell what the model should explain. I would like to see interactions between age and verb, and between age and the semantic predictors. According to p.20, "the main difference between 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6 year olds is simply an across the board decrease in the production of overgeneralization errors, rather than any change in their by-verb patterning." I would like to see a statistical evaluation of this claim.

3. Does the model predict how the behavior changes with age?

Differences in the model's construction activations across verbs are shown to correlate with differences in ratings, judgments and production probabilities of both children and adults (in at least some languages). However, it is not clear how much of what the model is capturing here is variance shared between children and adults. That is, the model might be capturing semantic effects on construction choice that are equally robust in adults and children. If the model can account for retreat from overgeneralization, it is important to show that the model predicts how the behavior *changes* across age. The fact that the model does not show a better fit to kid data early in training and a better fit to adult data late in training is problematic if the correlations reliably change across development. If they don't, then the authors should show that the model captures what *does* change, even if this is only a simple increase in the use of the rarer construction with age.

4. How important are semantics, verbs, and the causative node?

Assuming the model can account for the changes in construction use with age, I would like to see what is responsible for those changes in the model. In particular, the model could be lesioned by removing the verb nodes, semantic nodes and/or the causative node, or injecting noise into the representations or the connections involving these different inputs. From the statement on p.5 that there is only a small decrement in performance when the model is tested on novel verbs, it appears that most of the model's performance comes from capturing the semantic influences on construction choice. Would removing the verbs altogether reduce the model's performance? The causative node seems necessary to predict overgeneralization of the frequent construction early on, though a bias node might also work for that purpose.

Minor points:

5. Is there an interaction between directness and social desirability?

It seems to me that the social desirability effect would not disappear from calculating difference scores (p.7). The two constructions (at least in English) differ in directness of causation, so it seems plausible that socially undesirable actions would favor the periphrastic construction (as in "caused to die" vs. "killed"). Does social desirability not correlate with constructional choice? Would it make

sense to include it in the model as another cue?

6. Are the same semantic dimensions relevant to all languages?

There seems to be an assumption that the same four semantic dimensions should be relevant to the choice of the construction in all languages. I am curious as to whether this assumption is on a solid footing. It does not seem particularly surprising to me that there would be languages in which the choice of the causative construction is based on some variables other than the ones mentioned. Could this be the case in K'iche Mayan?

7. More description of the training corpora

More details on the training corpora are needed to evaluate whether they are representative of the input to children.

References

1. Kapatsinski V, Olejarczuk P, Redford MA: Perceptual Learning of Intonation Contour Categories in Adults and 9- to 11-Year-Old Children: Adults Are More Narrow-Minded. *Cogn Sci.* **41** (2): 383-415 [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Erker D, Guy G: The role of lexical frequency in syntactic variability: Variable subject personal pronoun expression in Spanish. *Language.* 2012; **88** (3): 526-557 [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My research deals with the role of domain-general learning mechanisms in language acquisition.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have

significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 07 Jan 2022

Ben Ambridge, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK

We thank this reviewer for their very helpful comments. In particular, the prompt to investigate the extent to which the model can explain the *retreat* from overgeneralization developmentally inspired new modeling work that caused us to rethink exactly what the model is telling us. Reviewer comments in italics.

This article reports novel data on overgeneralization, a core topic in the acquisition of language. It expands a prior study by the researchers to a younger age range. An important strength of this paper is the cross-linguistic breadth of the investigation, which is unprecedented except for the paper's companion piece (Ambridge et al., 2020). The main weakness of the paper is that the authors do not show that their computational model can account for the developmental trajectory. This is important because the main claim of the paper is that the model provides an account of retreat from overgeneralization. A second, related weakness of the analyses is that the authors say very little about how performance changes with age. Third, assuming that the model does account for the developmental trajectory, it would be important to show why it does. I elaborate on these issues below. Major points: 1. What properties of the computational model are important to account for the behavior? The computational model used in this paper is a simple two-layer connectionist network, in which the input consists of a local (one-hot) encoding of verb identity, and 4 continuous semantic parameters thought to be relevant to the choice between the causative constructions. Based on the preceding paper by the authors (Ambridge et al., 2020), the model also has an input node that represents whether the input is causative. The existence of this node is likely crucial for predicting that the more frequent causative construction will be overgeneralized, until the associations of specific semantic and lexical cues strengthen enough to override this initial bias. The output layer consists of three nodes for direct causative, indirect causative and 'other'. The learning rule is not described here, but is said to be a variant of Widrow-Hoff in Ambridge et al. (2020). It seems likely that the discriminative nature of this learning rule is crucial for the performance of the model, but this is not shown or discussed. It is also possible that a simple Hebbian learning rule would also do. It is important to provide a full description of the model here so that the work could be replicated, and the paper could be read as a stand-alone piece. A full description should include: the learning rule, the activation function on the output node, learning rate, and any other parameters that were set. The authors also need to describe whether they have attempted to use different learning rules, activation functions, or parameter settings. Such explorations would be very informative for determining what properties of the model are responsible for its ability to explain the human behavior. In particular, does it matter that the learning rule is discriminative?

Author Response: We have now added detail of this modeling (see section "Because we adopt the same model..."), which in fact involves clearing up some errors in the description of the old model (in fact, the learning rule is BFGS). We did not formally experiment with parameter settings in this model, but have now added a new modeling section (Study 3) in which we did this extensively.

2. How does the behavior change with age? It is not clear how the behavior in question changes with age. There are several possibilities, none of which are mutually exclusive. First, it could be

that the children are more accepting of deviation from prior experience than adults (e.g., Kapatsinski et al., 2017)¹. It could also be that children are gradually picking up on the semantic predictors conditioning the choice of the construction (Goldberg, 2019). Finally, it is also possible that, with age, children become more confident in their estimates of how individual verbs behave (e.g., suggested by Erker & Guy, 2012) Without knowing what changes with age, we cannot tell what the model should explain. I would like to see interactions between age and verb, and between age and the semantic predictors. According to p.20, "the main difference between 4;0-5;0 and 5;6-6;6 year olds is simply an across the board decrease in the production of overgeneralization errors, rather than any change in their by-verb patterning." I would like to see a statistical evaluation of this claim.

Author Response: This is a very important point. In the new version, we find that, actually, not much changes with age: The relevant interactions, which we have now added (see Table 6) show that only for English and Hebrew are older children's production data more adultlike than younger children's. This links to the next point...

3. Does the model predict how the behavior changes with age? Differences in the model's construction activations across verbs are shown to correlate with differences in ratings, judgments and production probabilities of both children and adults (in at least some languages). However, it is not clear how much of what the model is capturing here is variance shared between children and adults. That is, the model might be capturing semantic effects on construction choice that are equally robust in adults and children. If the model can account for retreat from overgeneralization, it is important to show that the model predicts how the behavior changes across age. The fact that the model does not show a better fit to kid data early in training and a better fit to adult data late in training is problematic if the correlations reliably change across development. If they don't, then the authors should show that the model captures what does change, even if this is only a simple increase in the use of the rarer construction with age.

Author Response: Yes, the reviewer's more pessimistic assessment is correct here. The model indeed seems to be capturing semantic (and lexical) effects on construction choice that are robust in adults and children. It does NOT seem to be able to account for development, even when it is extensively modified in ways that might allow it to do so (Study 3). Thus the modeling work suggests that although it provides a good account of how learners ultimately acquire verbs' restrictions, the model does not simulate the retreat from overgeneralization itself, which likely requires an explanation from outside the grammar. We discuss this extensively in the new version, but especially in the General Discussion.

4. How important are semantics, verbs, and the causative node? Assuming the model can account for the changes in construction use with age, I would like to see what is responsible for those changes in the model. In particular, the model could be lesioned by removing the verb nodes, semantic nodes and/or the causative node, or injecting noise into the representations or the connections involving these different inputs. From the statement on p.5 that there is only a small decrement in performance when the model is tested on novel verbs, it appears that most of the model's performance comes from capturing the semantic influences on construction choice. Would removing the verbs altogether reduce the model's performance? The causative node seems necessary to predict overgeneralization of the frequent construction early on, though a bias node might also work for that purpose.

Author Response: In the new modeling section (Study 3), we ran over 2,000 different

models including randomizing the semantics nodes and impairing the model's performance in various "childlike" ways. We did not, however, specifically try removing (a) the lexical verb nodes or (b) the causative node because this would correspond to scenarios in which the child (a) does not know the lexical form of the verb (which cannot be realistic, if the child is saying the verb) or (b) does not intend a causative message (which cannot be realistic, as the aim is to investigate what children say when they do have a causative message in mind). Importantly, NONE of our modifications allowed the model to predict the child data better than the adult data, which is why we conclude that the retreat from overgeneralization likely requires additional explanation from outside the grammar.

Minor points: 5. Is there an interaction between directness and social desirability? It seems to me that the social desirability effect would not disappear from calculating difference scores (p.7). The two constructions (at least in English) differ in directness of causation, so it seems plausible that socially undesirable actions would favor the periphrastic construction (as in "caused to die" vs. "killed"). Does social desirability not correlate with constructional choice? Would it make sense to include it in the model as another cue?

Author Response: In the new version we included valence ratings and R2 is exactly right here: "for Japanese and K'iche'... children are heavily influenced by valence (also significant for Hindi): The less acceptable the action, the more children prefer the more transparent form; (e.g., making something break, which hints at unintentionality, is more acceptable than breaking something, which suggests a more intentional act)".

6. Are the same semantic dimensions relevant to all languages? There seems to be an assumption that the same four semantic dimensions should be relevant to the choice of the construction in all languages. I am curious as to whether this assumption is on a solid footing. It does not seem particularly surprising to me that there would be languages in which the choice of the causative construction is based on some variables other than the ones mentioned. Could this be the case in K'iche Mayan?

Author Response: This could well be the case, but we did not investigate any semantic dimensions other than those discussed here, it would not be particularly informative for us to speculate.

7. More description of the training corpora More details on the training corpora are needed to evaluate whether they are representative of the input to children.

Author Response: The corpus data used in the previous version were not representative of speech to children, but we have now included an "Adult- versus Child-directed speech" manipulation (see subheading of this name) for English, Hebrew and Japanese (no suitable corpora were available for Hindi and K'iche'). References

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 29 April 2021

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Summary

In this work, the authors expand on a model presented in Ambridge *et al.*, 2020, which predicts causative alternation acceptability on a verb-by-verb basis. This model takes as its input both corpus data as well as adults' semantic feature ratings for the verbs in question. In the present paper, the model is expanded to account for young children's overgeneralization errors (e.g. "I'm dancing it" to mean "I'm causing it to dance"), both in offline comprehension and production. Notably, the authors attempt to account for children's overgeneralizations across five languages, and find that the Ambridge *et al.*, 2020 model correlates with children's performance in most cases. These findings, they conclude, provide evidence that the discriminative learning model in question is a plausible explanation for how children retreat from verb argument structure overgeneralization errors, on mechanistic level.

Major Comments

To begin with, the 23 authors of this study should undoubtedly be commended for the large-scale collaborative effort this study represents! It's also exciting to see computational research that does not shy away from fine-grained cross-linguistic comparison. The question the authors target in this work, how do children retreat from overgeneralization errors, is timely and relevant to the field, and overall their methodology seems sound. That said, there are 4 major areas of concern the authors should address in order to both make their precise claims more intelligible in the current work and to make their conclusions more convincing:

1. Disconnect between the data presented and the research questions.

a) The authors state in their abstract that "the present study demonstrates that a simple discriminative learning model ... constitutes a plausible mechanistic account of the retreat from overgeneralization." (p2) and later that "the problem of how language learners come to appropriately constrain their argument structure generalization looks close to being solved" (p22) because the model results correlate with both children and adults' causative judgment data and

children's causative productions. However, it's not explicitly stated how the present model instantiates the mechanisms for learning argument structure. Looking at the 2020 paper, it seems that the answer is approximately that children are using a combination of lexical-semantic features, a causal/non-causal binary operator, and the ability to identify the particular lexical items to intuit which causative verbs ought to alternate which way. And this conclusion is reached because the model in question approximates human performance using these particular pieces of information as input. For this paper to function as a stand-alone work, these connections ought to be spelled out here as well.

b) If the model presented is trained on the exact same data as the model in Ambridge *et al.*, 2020, what changed between the two papers is just the values of the dependent measure the model is expected to approximate. If the model successfully predicts adult judgments, it may only explain child judgments to the extent that they mirror adult judgments. And these would be all the cases where children are not making overgeneralization errors. Therefore, to what extent does the model provide a mechanistic explanation for the retreat from overgeneralization? Perhaps a more direct measure of how well the model captures overgeneralization itself would be to correlate model performance, for each verb, with verb-level estimates of children's overgeneralizations (baselined to adults judgments).

c) Furthermore, the 2020 paper did test the model on data from children, just slightly older ones (5-6 year-olds and 9-10 year-olds). The contribution of the current work is that the children tested were a bit younger still, at 4;0-5;0. The question this raises is: What are the data from these slightly younger children adding to our inferences about underlying generalizations? The authors state that "the majority of [children's] overgeneralization errors are produced before [they're 5 years old]" (page 5). It would be helpful to more clearly spell out how testing children in the year before that allows us to make new inferences beyond those made in the 2020 paper.

2. Concerns about children's acceptability judgments and judgment data

a) The authors note that "the researchers who worked with the children reported that... children rat[ed] sentences, to some extent, on the basis of the social desirability of the events described" (p7). This, they reason, may have accounted for some undergeneralization errors such as children's low ratings for "someone broke the truck." This raises questions about the validity of the grammaticality judgments and priming task in general. To what extent does the binary decision assessment conflate social desirability and grammatical acceptability? While the words in Figures 1-3 are a bit difficult to read, it seems possible that the more overgeneralized verbs correspond to more positively-valenced ones (e.g. dance, sing, play). It seems that the authors take the correlations with adult data to be evidence that children were attending to the grammatical acceptability on the whole, but it would be more convincing to show, say, a lack of correlation between child judgments and a valance measure.

b) The authors convincingly demonstrate that children's acceptability judgments correlate with those of adults. They take this to mean that "at least for English-, Hebrew-, Hindi- and K'iche'-speaking, children were indeed giving meaningful judgments" (p7). However, it should be noted that if children's responses are highly similar to adults', and the model used here has already been shown to reliably predict adults' judgement data, the mere correlation of model results and child judgment data should not be taken as a necessarily new finding, though this correlation appears

to be the main result for Experiment 1. Simply put – if the model predictions correlate with adult data, and adult response data correlates with child response data, why wouldn't we expect the model predictions to correlate with the child data? Indeed, for the Japanese data where the child and adult responses do not correlate, the model does not appear to capture the child judgments.

Additionally, the semantic feature judgments that serve as input to the model appear to be judgments from adults. It seems reasonable to assume that children's judgments will not match adults' – even in this paper, there are instances where authors voice concerns about children not interpreting the valence of the sentences in an adult-like way (as just discussed). If the model is to be taken as a mechanistic explanation for how children retreat from their errors, it seems necessary to have its input parallel children's mental state as much as possible. The worry is that since the model relies on adult judgments, it might be ascribing to children knowledge that they do not yet possess. The model may therefore approximate children's binary judgment data for the wrong reason (it's relying on semantic information adults are privy to but children aren't). To avoid these concerns, the authors could provide some evidence for why they expect that children's and adults' semantic feature judgments would either match, or differ in a non-meaningful way.

3. Concerns about how to interpret the correlations.

The verb-level correlations from child and adult performance ignore the subject-level variability of estimates. If the data were analyzed instead with mixed-effects models (where verb is a random-effects variable), would adult ratings predict children's (and vice versa)?

4. Concerns about the model data being run using adult corpus data

a) For both studies, it appears that the authors ran the Ambridge *et al.*, 2020 model on causative alternation data gleaned from adult speech, and not speech to children. Given that the model is concluded to provide a potential mechanistic explanation for children's retreat from overgeneralization, it seems right to include causative alternation frequencies present in the speech that children themselves hear. Or at least, some evidence that the frequencies don't differ in the two types of speech is needed.

b) Finally, it's not clear from the present work that the semantic input nodes were necessary aspects of the model. Is it possible that the corpus frequencies just mapped on well to adults' and children's judgments? The opposite could also be asked – was the corpus frequency data needed in addition to the semantic features?

Minor Comments

1. Where possible, it'd be helpful to have vectorized images for the figures, or at least larger files. As is, it is difficult to read the individual words in Figures 1-3 and 9-10. Figure 11, while legible, is also a bit blurry. Once the figures are reproduced in higher definition it may additionally be useful to display the words in such a way that they don't overlap on Figures 1-3 & 9-10 (perhaps with a slight jitter).

2. Page 3-4 – A list of citations is given for papers and books that have investigated overgeneralization errors in English. While it's helpful to have a collection of citations for the past work on these errors, there is no explicit characterization of what this work has concluded. In order to show that it's relevant to the specific question of how learners overcome these errors, some curation of these citations is necessary.
3. Page 4 – A trio of theories are introduced here “preemption, conservatism via entrenchment (both statistical-learning theories) and verb semantics.” It seems to be a main goal of this work to show that these theories (or at least the unified version) provide the correct account of children's retreat from overgeneralization errors, so it would be helpful to give a precise definition for them here, as well as provide citations for their use. While this section is summarizing Ambridge *et al.*, 2020, it becomes difficult to evaluate the main conclusions in the present paper on its own without (re)articulating these theories and how the model instantiates a combination of the three.
4. Page 11 – The authors make reference to the notion that “social desirability may be particularly salient in the more collectivist Japanese culture” in their explanation for the lack of correlation between the child and adult judgments for the Japanese data. While they provide a citation to this effect, this explanation appears to be a bit vague. In order to avoid being reductive in including cultural collectivism as a possible explanation, it'd be necessary to first establish that the cultures of other children in this study are less collectivist (and there is at least some evidence that this is a false assumption, e.g. Oyserman, Coon, & Kemmelmeier, 2002). Barring evidence to this effect, the cultural explanation doesn't convincingly explain the data pattern.
5. Page 20 – The authors state: “Comparison of Figure 9 (4;0-5;0) and Figure 10 (5;6-6;6) indicates that, by this later age, overgeneralization errors have all but ceased for English, Hindi and Japanese, and decreased considerably for Hebrew.” However, this difference is not particularly obvious from cross-figure comparison. A single figure comparing the results from both age groups on one graph (or at least closer together on a page) for each language would highlight this better.

Typesetting

For Figures 4-8 & 11, the labels could be cleaned up a bit (e.g. spaces added instead of underscores).

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My co-reviewer and I have expertise in language development and psycholinguistics, specifically in the area of argument structure.

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however we have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 07 Jan 2022

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We thank these reviewers for their very helpful comments. In particular, the prompt to investigate the extent to which the model can explain the *retreat* from overgeneralization developmentally inspired new modeling work that caused us to rethink exactly what the model is telling us. Reviewer comments in italics.

Summary: In this work, the authors expand on a model presented in Ambridge et al., 2020, which predicts causative alternation acceptability on a verb-by-verb basis. This model takes as its input both corpus data as well as adults' semantic feature ratings for the verbs in question. In the present paper, the model is expanded to account for young children's overgeneralization errors (e.g. "I'm dancing it" to mean "I'm causing it to dance"), both in offline comprehension and production. Notably, the authors attempt to account for children's overgeneralizations across five languages, and find that the Ambridge et al., 2020 model correlates with children's performance in most cases. These findings, they conclude, provide evidence that the discriminative learning model in question is a plausible explanation for how children retreat from verb argument structure overgeneralization errors, on mechanistic level. Major Comments To begin with, the 23 authors of this study should undoubtedly be commended for the large-scale collaborative effort this study represents! It's also exciting to see computational research that does not shy away from fine-grained cross-linguistic comparison. The question the authors target in this work, how do children retreat from overgeneralization errors, is timely and relevant to the field, and overall their methodology seems sound. That said, there are 4 major areas of concern the authors should address in order to both make their precise claims more intelligible in the current work and to make their conclusions more convincing: 1. Disconnect between the data presented and the research questions. a) The authors state in their abstract that "the present study demonstrates that a simple discriminative learning model ... constitutes a plausible mechanistic account of the retreat from overgeneralization." (p2) and later that "the problem of how language learners come to appropriately constrain their argument structure generalization looks close to being solved" (p22) because the model results correlate with both children and adults' causative judgment data and children's causative productions. However, it's not explicitly stated how the present model instantiates the mechanisms for learning argument structure. Looking at the 2020 paper, it seems that the answer is approximately that children are using a combination

of lexical-semantic features, a causal/non-causal binary operator, and the ability to identify the particular lexical items to intuit which causative verbs ought to alternate which way. And this conclusion is reached because the model in question approximates human performance using these particular pieces of information as input. For this paper to function as a stand-alone work, these connections ought to be spelled out here as well.

Author Response: We have added detail about how the model worked, and how it instantiates mechanisms for learning argument structure; See sections beginning “Rather, the model was trained to “predict” the forms...” and “Because we adopt the same model in the present article, it is important to fully set out here the details of its architecture.”

b) If the model presented is trained on the exact same data as the model in Ambridge et al., 2020, what changed between the two papers is just the values of the dependent measure the model is expected to approximate. If the model successfully predicts adult judgments, it may only explain child judgments to the extent that they mirror adult judgments. And these would be all the cases where children are not making overgeneralization errors. Therefore, to what extent does the model provide a mechanistic explanation for the retreat from overgeneralization? Perhaps a more direct measure of how well the model captures overgeneralization itself would be to correlate model performance, for each verb, with verb-level estimates of children's overgeneralizations (baselined to adults judgments).

Author Response: In the previous version of this paper, and in Ambridge et al (2020), we rather overstated the success of the model by conflating two questions (1) Does the model eventually come to mirror adults' judgments and (2) Does it, along the way, show a similar by-verb overgeneralization-than-retreat pattern to children. In fact, although the answer to the first question is yes, the answer to the second question is no. We discuss this throughout the new version, but most explicitly in the General Discussion (section beginning “At one level...”)

c) Furthermore, the 2020 paper did test the model on data from children, just slightly older ones (5-6 year-olds and 9-10 year-olds). The contribution of the current work is that the children tested were a bit younger still, at 4;0-5;0. The question this raises is: What are the data from these slightly younger children adding to our inferences about underlying generalizations? The authors state that “the majority of [children's] overgeneralization errors are produced before [they're 5 years old]” (page 5). It would be helpful to more clearly spell out how testing children in the year before that allows us to make new inferences beyond those made in the 2020 paper.

Author Response: The most important contribution in the present article is not so much the binary grammaticality judgments – which, we acknowledge do not really do much more than bring the age down a bit – but the production data. These data are important to address the potential concern that acceptability judgments are a meta-linguistic task that do not provide a reliable measure of children's knowledge and/or performance. It is therefore important to show, as the new version does, that the model (and the new models) predict production data as well as just judgment data.

2. Concerns about children's acceptability judgments and judgment data a) The authors note that “the researchers who worked with the children reported that... children rat[ed] sentences, to some extent, on the basis of the social desirability of the events described” (p7). This, they reason, may have accounted for some undergeneralization errors such as children's low ratings for “someone broke the truck.” This raises questions about the validity of the grammaticality judgments and

priming task in general. To what extent does the binary decision assessment conflate social desirability and grammatical acceptability? While the words in Figures 1-3 are a bit difficult to read, it seems possible that the more overgeneralized verbs correspond to more positively-valenced ones (e.g. dance, sing, play). It seems that the authors take the correlations with adult data to be evidence that children were attending to the grammatical acceptability on the whole, but it would be more convincing to show, say, a lack of correlation between child judgments and a valence measure.

Author Response: We have added analyses showing that, in many cases there IS indeed a correlation with a valence measure (see “Verb valence ratings (from Warriner...)”). This is particularly the case for Japanese and K’iche’ binary judgment data, which could well be a reason why children’s binary judgments do not correlate well with adults’ for these languages). However, for English, Hebrew and Hindi the significant correlations for binary judgment data reported in the previous version (now “upgraded” to mixed-effects models) survive the introduction of valence ratings as a control predictor. No valence effects are observed for the production data; it seems they are a consequence of asking children to rate forms for “acceptability” – and failing to fully ensure that they understand this to mean purely “grammatical” acceptability.

b) The authors convincingly demonstrate that children’s acceptability judgments correlate with those of adults. They take this to mean that “at least for English-, Hebrew-, Hindi- and K’iche’-speaking, children were indeed giving meaningful judgments” (p7). However, it should be noted that if children’s responses are highly similar to adults’, and the model used here has already been shown to reliably predict adults’ judgement data, the mere correlation of model results and child judgment data should not be taken as a necessarily new finding, though this correlation appears to be the main result for Experiment 1. Simply put – if the model predictions correlate with adult data, and adult response data correlates with child response data, why wouldn’t we expect the model predictions to correlate with the child data? Indeed, for the Japanese data where the child and adult responses do not correlate, the model does not appear to capture the child judgments.

Author Response: Certainly, given that (a) the model predicts adult data and (b) children’s data are highly correlated with adult data, we would certainly expect to see that the model predicts children’s data. The more interesting question is not simply DOES the model predict children’s data, but the EXTENT to which it predicts children’s data. The fact that the model (including in all its additional versions; new for this revised version) predicts children’s data LESS well than adults is important and interesting, as it suggests that – as we note throughout this new paper – the solution to the retreat from overgeneralization seems to live outside the grammar.

Additionally, the semantic feature judgments that serve as input to the model appear to be judgments from adults. It seems reasonable to assume that children’s judgments will not match adults’ – even in this paper, there are instances where authors voice concerns about children not interpreting the valence of the sentences in an adult-like way (as just discussed). If the model is to be taken as a mechanistic explanation for how children retreat from their errors, it seems necessary to have its input parallel children’s mental state as much as possible. The worry is that since the model relies on adult judgments, it might be ascribing to children knowledge that they do not yet possess. The model may therefore approximate children’s binary judgment data for the wrong reason (it’s relying on semantic information adults are privy to but children aren’t). To

avoid these concerns, the authors could provide some evidence for why they expect that children's and adults' semantic feature judgments would either match, or differ in a non-meaningful way.

Author Response: We would certainly agree that children's semantic knowledge is unlikely to be adultlike, but we are not aware of any directly relevant evidence on this issue. So, rather than simply speculate, we have introduced a new modeling section ("Study 3: Further computational modeling") in which we attempt to "instantiate various limitations that correspond to those facing children". Most relevantly, we include no-semantics models in which this information is removed, to investigate whether it is possible to learn these restrictions in a purely lexical way. Other manipulations are also indicative here, including "dropout" which simulates – amongst other things – missing or incomplete semantic information.

3. Concerns about how to interpret the correlations. The verb-level correlations from child and adult performance ignore the subject-level variability of estimates. If the data were analyzed instead with mixed-effects models (where verb is a random-effects variable), would adult ratings predict children's (and vice versa)?

Author Response: Yes, this is an important point: In the new version we now report mixed-effects models rather than simple by-verb correlations, for both the binary-judgment and production studies.

4. Concerns about the model data being run using adult corpus data a) For both studies, it appears that the authors ran the Ambridge et al., 2020 model on causative alternation data gleaned from adult speech, and not speech to children. Given that the model is concluded to provide a potential mechanistic explanation for children's retreat from overgeneralization, it seems right to include causative alternation frequencies present in the speech that children themselves hear. Or at least, some evidence that the frequencies don't differ in the two types of speech is needed.

Author Response: We have now introduced versions of the model based on child-directed speech (see "Adult- versus Child-directed speech"), for the languages for which suitable corpora were available (English, Hebrew and Japanese).

b) Finally, it's not clear from the present work that the semantic input nodes were necessary aspects of the model. Is it possible that the corpus frequencies just mapped on well to adults' and children's judgments? The opposite could also be asked – was the corpus frequency data needed in addition to the semantic features?

Author Response: As noted above, we have now run models with neutralized semantic information, but it is not possible to remove corpus frequency information because training the model on a flat distribution would involve training it on ungrammatical utterances with the same frequency as grammatical utterances. This is not only unrealistic, but changes the "right answer" that the model is attempting to learn. E.g., if we presented "Someone made the boy laugh" and "*Someone laughed the boy" with equal frequency, we are effectively telling the model that the two forms are equally grammatical, which would entail specifically designing it to learn a language with different properties to the natural languages included in the present study.

Minor Comments 1. Where possible, it'd be helpful to have vectorized images for the figures, or at least larger files. As is, it is difficult to read the individual words in Figures 1-3 and 9-10. Figure

11, while legible, is also a bit blurry. Once the figures are reproduced in higher definition it may additionally be useful to display the words in such a way that they don't overlap on Figures 1-3 & 9-10 (perhaps with a slight jitter).

Author Response: Yes, we have fixed this and now supply PDF files instead.

2. Page 3-4 – A list of citations is given for papers and books that have investigated overgeneralization errors in English. While it's helpful to have a collection of citations for the past work on these errors, there is no explicit characterization of what this work has concluded. In order to show that it's relevant to the specific question of how learners overcome these errors, some curation of these citations is necessary.

Author Response: We have now done this in the section beginning "Previous studies had attempted to explain this phenomenon..."

3. Page 4 – A trio of theories are introduced here "preemption, conservatism via entrenchment (both statistical-learning theories) and verb semantics." It seems to be a main goal of this work to show that these theories (or at least the unified version) provide the correct account of children's retreat from overgeneralization errors, so it would be helpful to give a precise definition for them here, as well as provide citations for their use. While this section is summarizing Ambridge et al., 2020, it becomes difficult to evaluate the main conclusions in the present paper on its own without (re)articulating these theories and how the model instantiates a combination of the three.

Author Response: The same section now also defines these terms.

4. Page 11 – The authors make reference to the notion that "social desirability may be particularly salient in the more collectivist Japanese culture" in their explanation for the lack of correlation between the child and adult judgments for the Japanese data. While they provide a citation to this effect, this explanation appears to be a bit vague. In order to avoid being reductive in including cultural collectivism as a possible explanation, it'd be necessary to first establish that the cultures of other children in this study are less collectivist (and there is at least some evidence that this is a false assumption, e.g. Oyserman, Coon, & Kemmelmeier, 2002). Barring evidence to this effect, the cultural explanation doesn't convincingly explain the data pattern.

Author Response: We have removed this passage because in fact the newly-introduced valence predictor predicts children's data (on the binary judgment task) for Hindi and K'iche' as well as Japanese, so a cultural explanation does not seem likely here.

5. Page 20 – The authors state: "Comparison of Figure 9 (4;0-5;0) and Figure 10 (5;6-6;6) indicates that, by this later age, overgeneralization errors have all but ceased for English, Hindi and Japanese, and decreased considerably for Hebrew." However, this difference is not particularly obvious from cross-figure comparison. A single figure comparing the results from both age groups on one graph (or at least closer together on a page) for each language would highlight this better.

Author Response: The figures are already very busy, so we have not been able to combine them into a single plot; but we hope the typesetter will align them closely on the page to allow for such comparison to be possible.

Typesetting For Figures 4-8 & 11, the labels could be cleaned up a bit (e.g. spaces added instead of underscores).

Author Response: Done – thanks!

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
